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Visualized experiences of the affordances

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INTRODUCTION

The successful design, development, and implementation of nature-based solutions (NBS) depends largely on their usability and accessibility for different participants. This requires an understanding of the affordances of NBS sites and the needs of different participant groups. For this task we have found affordance and umwelt analysis to be appropriate tools. In the context of the Coevolvers project LL's, improving affordances and enabling better access to them has turned out to be a key method for NBS development. As Coevolvers support mutual learning and co-creation, we also pay attention to how participants create affordances for each other and interact through the affordances. The aim of the report is to give an overview of the theory and methodology of studying affordances and umwelts in multi-species environments, to give an overview of the use of this approach in LL's and to suggest methods of making affordances visible for NBS planning, development.

For this project, affordances are understood as properties of the places (but also living organisms, artefacts, and institutions) that enable human or non-human subjects to participate in NBS. Our approach is based on the original conceptualisation of James J. Gibson: "The affordances of the environment are what it offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes, either for good or ill" (Gibson 1979[1986]: 127). Understanding, analysing and mapping affordances is central to the development of NBS. However, this is not a straightforward process. Affordances are always affordances to someone, related to their physiology, knowledge, capacities, and life needs. Sites of NBS in most cases include a multitude of biological species, which entails the need to analyse many meaningful connections between non-human others and environmental affordances. We are not able to experience affordances for others directly but need tools to make them visible. This is possible with the help of umwelt theory and semiotic modelling (see sections 1.2, 1.4).

Mapping and visualizing affordances in the context of NBS therefore involves two transformative processes. First, affordances for human and non-human participants are initially hidden and obscured. An umwelt-based methodology enables meaningful connections between non-humans and the places where NBS are being developed to be perceived and analysed. In this report we, like Gibson (1979[1986]), consider affordances as a multi-species phenomenon. The second transformation is to translate and express affordances for socio-cultural discourses and human decision-making in ways that are understandable and valued. In sum, the methodology presented in this report can be seen as a tool for systematizing experiences of affordances.

Affordances play a major role in the development of NBS. Discovering hidden affordances and developing them has a great capacity for NBS. Sites of NBS have "affordance potential". Affordances function as links through which different participants (human and non-human) interact and negotiate their relationships. Participants can provide affordances for each other or become affordances for each other. Knowing and using these connections could make NBS more accessible to non-human others and vulnerable groups.

For these reasons it is essential to include non-human others in affordance analysis and visualization. Most NBS involve other species in some way, and the concept itself suggests the inclusion of more than human interactions. If our goal is to solve social

and economic problems by working with natural systems, this is unlikely to be achieved without involving other species in the planning, implementation, and management of NBS. In doing this also the needs and interests of nonhuman species needs to be described and included. Unfortunately, there are currently insufficient opportunities for the social and cultural representation of other species in human decision-making processes. This is another key issue in the development of NBS that this report aims to address. The visualisations will be achieved by combining methods of semiotic translation with tools of cultural and artistic representations. By providing methods for visualizing affordances that evokes experience and empathy, the report leads to better representation of non-humans (section 5).

The current report includes an overview of the theoretical foundations, an introduction to the umwelt-based place analysis (the original outcome of Task 3.2), examples of its application in different living labs, analyses of the conflicts, missing affordances and potentials, and suggestions for visualizing umwelts and affordances for human decision making. The report makes extensive use of the collaboration and experience gained from different Work Packages, Tasks and Living Labs: The report builds on theoretical insights from WP2, Task 2.2, by working with Living Lab sites using participatory and co-creative methods in Task 3.1, and by using information gathered through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews in Task 4.1. There is an ongoing collaboration with WP1 (Task 1.2 and 1.3.) to produce novel methods and digital tools for data collection. The current report and the results of Task 3.2 will lead to the mapping and understanding of vulnerabilities (Task 3.3) and the co-design of policies and governance models (WP 4, Task 4.2).

In more practical terms of the workflow, Tartu Living Lab (LL) was used as a pilot area to develop the methodology, with several research visits to the area, conference "Contemporary Umwelt Analysis: Applications for Culture and Ecological Relations" (Tartu, Estonia, 17–19 April, 2023), workshops on non-human perspectives, and sensory walks. Students from the MA course "Semiotic Analysis of the Environment" at the University of Tartu were involved in the development and testing of the methodology in the spring of 2024. The cooperation was established with Tartu city government, and the project provided analysis and information for future development of the Ülejõe district. In parallel, a series of digital consultations were held with other project partners to identify the specific needs of the selected Living Labs (Turku 21.06.2023, 6.11.2023, 05.03.2024; Sardinia 1.06.2023, 11.12.2023, 21.02.2024; Hutton 12.05.2023, 28.11.2023, 13.03.2024, Catalonia 5.06.2023). The methodology was adapted accordingly by focusing on: (1) ecosocial compensation for Turku Living Lab (2) connections between affordances, umwelts and mindfulness for Sardinia Living Lab (3) forest ecosystem, multisensory experience and digital mediation for Hutton Living Lab. Methodological tools used in the analysis included umwelt cards, photovoice, walking interviews, umwelt awareness exercises and storytelling events.

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES

1.1 The place, value, and potential of non-humans in NBS

As per the European Commission's delimitation of NBS, they "must /.../ benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services." Despite the criticisms of nature-based solutions as anthropocentric (e.g., Maller 2021), the considerations of non-humans are present in the aims set for NBSs, at least on a conceptual level. However, as the quote above demonstrates, the reconcilability of human and non-human needs and interests is taken as a given, implying that enhanced biodiversity will simultaneously support various human needs-based ecosystem services. While this might often be the case, *assuming a default win-win situation overlooks cases where conflicts with human stakeholders arise in biodiversity enhancement efforts or vice versa, where the human-centred ecosystem services are not necessarily tied to the interests of other species*. These conflicts can involve non-humans pursuing their own agendas that conflict with human interests, or humans rejecting the consideration of non-human needs in planned environmental transformations.

Moreover, biodiversity is not just about the number of species; it is also about the diversity of ways different organisms relate to their environments and each other (structural diversity) and the evolutionary potential they provide. This aspect should be highlighted when considering non-humans in the context of NBS, as non-humans are often instrumentalized when discussing the benefits of biodiversity for humans, with their own interests and needs left unattended. However, if NBS are to be aligned with multispecies justice or ecological justice frameworks, a more bio/ecocentric approach to human-induced environmental transformations is needed (Pineda-Pinto et al 2023). The explicit inclusion of non-human perspectives in NBS allows:

- 1) Questioning the scope of applicability of certain NBS, specifying the locations and contexts where they might work. Considering non-humans would allow for assessing if a solution would be received similarly in a location with a different species composition or with human communities having entirely different relationships with specific non-humans.
- 2) Accounting for the history of existing human-non-human relations in a particular place, thereby considering the impact of a specific NBS in light of the trajectory of those relations.
- 3) Viewing organisms of local populations as agents, not just passive 'numbers' in species counts, thus recognizing them as participants in the co-creation of the NBS. Furthermore, nonhuman local populations can be considered as vulnerable groups in the context of NBS, taking into account the specifics of their abilities (movement, recognition, memory, etc).
- 4) Shedding light on the non-uniformity of human interests and values, both in their fundamental beliefs about human-environment relations (e.g., anthropocentrism vs. biocentrism) and in their relationships to individual species (e.g., urban bird feeders vs. those who see the same birds as nuisances), and being ready to take this variety into account when considering the acceptability of certain NBSs.

1.2 Umwelt theory – learning about needs of other species

There are three interconnected conceptual tools – umwelt, affordance and ecofield – that can be used for analysing the needs and role of non-human species in NBS. Umwelt can be thought of as the organism's model of the world or the set of distinctions made by an organism, i.e. self-world (Godfrey-Smith 2024). The aim of the umwelt analysis is to identify the organism's umwelt (to some approximation), i.e. the objects that are meaningful to the organism and the features by which the organism recognises these objects. The founder of umwelt theory was Baltic German biologist Jakob von Uexküll (1864–1944) (see e.g. Uexküll 2010). The concept of umwelt has been used in semiotics (Sebeok 1979, Uexküll, T von 1992, Kull, Lotman 1995, see also Tønnessen et al 2016), ethology (de Waal 2016, Burghardt 1990) and philosophy (e.g. Merleau-Ponty 2003 [1995], Canguilhem 2001 [1948], see also Michelini, Köchy 2020).

There are two important parts of the umwelt analysis. Firstly, the distinctions made by the organism, i.e. the modelling aspect of the organism's umwelt. Second, the set of affordances in the organism's habitat or set of possible uses of the environment. Depending on the research question, either the umwelt or the elements of the umwelt of individuals of a single species or the umwelts of several species, either separately or in a communicative situation in relation to each other, can be studied. Umwelt is originally designed to analyse experiential worlds of animals – organisms that distinguish meaningful locations in their surroundings. Umwelt approach can be adjusted to describe needs of trees, fungi, and other sessile organisms.

The analysis of the umwelt can rely on observations, experiments, comparisons, and modelling. Three types of knowledge are required for the analysis of the umwelt. First, knowledge of the (perceptual) morphology and physiology of the organism, i.e. what they are capable of perceiving. Second, knowledge of the animal's behaviour – what the animal reacts to, what objects they attribute meaning to. Thirdly, it is necessary to know which object features in the environment act as signs for the animal.

How to get this knowledge? The first thing to do is to look at the available literature – zoosemiotics, ethology, comparative anatomy and physiology, or even species-specific literature can provide information. Secondly, observations are needed to determine which objects and signs drive which behaviour. Experiments could also be needed to be sure which traits act as signs, but again these can be found in literature. Once the information is available, further analysis can be planned in a number of ways, depending on what is of central interest at the time. In all these analyses, it is also important to bear in mind the particularities of the researcher's umwelt, so as not to transfer them to the animal.

An analysis of the 'umwelt of single species', i.e. of all the meanings and sign sequences, requires an extensive body of knowledge and in-depth observations. It is almost impossible to describe the species' umwelt completely, at least for complex animals, because new connections are constantly being made through learning and experience, and so it can be said that the umwelt is constantly evolving. It is, however, possible to identify the predominant relationships and, on the basis of these, to predict what or with whom an animal might form relationships in the future.

We can take Uexküll's proposed four functional circles – food, partner, enemy and medium – as a starting point and map the objects, behavioural repertoires and behavioural drivers that are important to the animal accordingly. These four functional circles cover the most basic categories of meaning shared by different animal species, but this does not mean that all animals are based solely on these meanings. In the case of more complex species, meanings related to, for example, play, curiosity, etc. may be added.

1.3 Ecofields and affordances in multispecies environments

The umwelt analysis can go beyond the single species and map the meaning relations between an animal and the physical environment or meaning relations that several species have with the given place. In short observation, it is possible to determine the meaning of an entity (e.g. a bush, a rock, a tree trunk) for different animal species. A more detailed observation also allows to specify features of the entity that are important for different species. It is also possible to analyse what kind of interspecific relationships a given element promotes – for example, competition, commensalism, parasitism or symbiosis – and whether it also drives interspecific interactions or rather acts as a communication barrier. In addition, with the concept of affordances the object can be approached by asking what activities, and for which species, does the object in principle afford.

The affordance concept derives from American perceptual psychologist James J. Gibson (1979[1986]). He defines affordance as follows: “The affordances of the environment are what it offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes, either for good or ill” (Gibson 1979[1986]: 127). Affordance is the specific property or quality of the environment for its inhabitants. Most examples provided by Gibson are related to the physical activities of animals: a surface that affords support, terrain features such as slopes and steps that guide movement, and so on. Affordances can be seen as relative to the participant (human and non-human), connect subjective and objective aspects of NBS, can be ecological (in relations), social, cultural (access), can be negative (limiting, constraining) or positive (making possible), have temporary dimension and course (scaffolds). Thure von Uexküll and colleagues (1993: 13) suggest analysing affordances in the triadic framework: affordance (property of the environment), counter-affordance (capacity of an organism enabling use of the affordance), activity that creates connection between the two. This provides an important practical insight: even if the affordances are present, human or non-human participant also needs to have access, possibility and competences to harness the affordance. At the same time, participant may not be aware of the affordances that are always available – experiential or semiotic presence does not always indicate the presence of affordance. In a multispecies environment, affordance is a property of/in the environmental object that is useful or harmful for a large number of species. The affordances are often overlooked but can be made visible by umwelt analysis. It is also possible to take a more holistic approach, starting with the place or physical environment and observing which objects are mostly used or avoided there and which objects are not associated with almost any species. In this way, it is possible to identify the dominant features of

the environment – the objects that are used or avoided by many different species – and to analyze which features are most noticeable in these objects and how they differ between species. An analogy here is the concept of 'universal design', as we know it in architecture – design that appeals to as many social groups as possible. Similarly, by maintaining the dominant features of the environment, it is also possible to encourage the presence of different species in the same environment. This is an essential possibility for maintaining and supporting non-human animals in NBS.

If we are interested in the development of multispecies environments, such analysis should be complemented by an analysis of the ecofields of each species – i.e. whether a given environment provides only a few specific resources, or whether it functions as a holistic habitat where food, nesting and refuge sites can be found. For this aim, the ecofield analysis was developed by Italian landscape ecologist and semiotician Almo Farina (2008; Farina, Belgrano 2004). Ecofield analysis can be understood as a spatial extension of umwelt analysis. An ecofield analysis can be used to explain the environmental use of a selected animal species in terms of its functional needs, environmental perception and characteristics of the environment. Thus, an ecofield analysis allows an assessment of the functional and semiotic suitability of the environment for a given species by highlighting the presence and articulation of ecofields required by the species in a given environment. In cases where ecofield analysis is used to describe the environmental use of two or more species, the method allows the identification of areas where the different species meet, as well as potential sites of conflict between them.

Ecofield analysis builds on Uexküll's concepts of the umwelt and the functional cycle, according to which animals perceive and relate to the environment according to their life functions and behavioural motivations. Almo Farina and Andrea Belgrano (2004: 108) define ecofield as 'the physical (ecological) space and the associated abiotic and biotic properties perceived by a given species when its corresponding functional trait is active'. The notion of ecofield links the geographic properties of the habitat to the animal's life functions. An ecofield is "a spatial configuration that is meaningful to a species" (Farina 2008: 32). In this sense, the habitat of an individual member of species or local population is the sum of all its ecofields. Farina does not provide a comprehensive list of possible ecofields but mentions some of them in his work: guarding ecofield, foraging ecofield, drinking ecofield, navigating ecofield, breeding or reproduction ecofield, shelter or security ecofield (Farina, Belgrano 2006; Farina 2008). The security ecofield has been studied in more detail (Farina, James 2023). Human use of the environment can also be included in the analysis, in which case it is useful to distinguish, for example, religious ecofields, recreational ecofields, etc. (Farina et al. 2005). Thus, it is possible to use ecofield analysis to map human-animal relations in the context of NBS.

Almo Farina has positioning of the concept of the ecofield in relation to animal needs and environmental resources in the following sequence: need – function (behavioural application) – semiotic interface (ecofield) – resource (Farina 2012: 23). This clarification is important to highlight that the presence of an ecofield perceived by an animal in the environment does not always guarantee the presence or availability of the associated resources necessary for life and, on the contrary, sometimes the ecofield may be present but the corresponding resource may be either absent or

unavailable. As a methodological guideline, the ecofield concept requires attention to the categorisation and delimitation of ecofields. The method does not unambiguously define an exhaustive list of ecofields (recreational ecofields, nutritional ecofields, etc.), and the analyst is free to complete and refine it. Also, ecofields may be defined in the analysis in different scope (single tree, grove, forest). The categorisation and delimitation of ecological fields must be systematic. These three concepts – umwelt, affordance and ecofield – are in following applied in the practical methodology for analysing non-human involvement in NBS and visualizing affordances.

1.4 Semiotic modelling and biosemiotic translation

Our capacity to understand non-human animals affects how we can include them in social and political decision-making on NBS. Many species live outside of our awareness of them or cultural discourses about them. The main reason for this inaccessibility is that animals live in umwelts and communicate in ways that are inaccessible to us. Another obstacle to interpretation may be the difference in scale – micro-organisms – or different ecologies – it is difficult to perceive a life-cycle of parasitic organisms.

Semiotic modelling could help incorporate non-humans into human culture and translate their habits and needs into cultural discourses. Semiotic modelling is understood here as the analysis of the form, structure and function of cultural texts and artefacts, revealing their underlying assumptions, motivations or hidden connotative meanings and power relations. In the case of animal representations, semiotic modelling can reveal hidden oppositions (human-non-human animal), social allegories, anthropomorphisms, attribution of negative meanings (scapegoating) and similar features.

It is also possible to use semiotic modelling to create narratives that more effectively and appropriately represent non-humans in human social processes. Such artistic texts are condensed and intense forms of conveying information (Lotman 1977). One way of establishing a connection with non-human species, based on linguistic connection and narrative creation, would be biotranslation. The concept of biotranslation was proposed in 2003 in a paper by biosemiotics professor Kalevi Kull and cultural semiotics professor Peeter Torop. They understand biotranslation as a situation in which „some signs in one umwelt are put into a correspondence with some signs in another umwelt. [...] For it to be possible for translation to occur, there must be a certain connection, or overlapping, between the umwelten” (Kull, Torop 2003: 318).

The basis of biotranslation can be similarities and analogies between umwelts and ecological codes as partially shared communication conventions in an ecosystem (Maran 2020a). We can interpret other animals on the basis of biotranslational logic to the extent that humans and other animals relate and communicate at the level of prelinguistic modelling, that is, through the cycles of sensory perceptions and behaviours. In order to use the concept of umwelt to establish contact with other species, it is important to recognise that authors, readers and translators also have their own species-specific human umwelt. Biosemiotic properties that relate the author

or reader to other species are embodiment, physiological processes, way of moving, biological needs and functions, fragility of the body, fear of pain and death, different senses and communication channels that the author uses to communicate with the environment.

From this we could deduce that a similarity base between overlapping umwelts is any constructive property that can serve as a cognitive link to build an overlap. Examples of similarity basis that can become basis of cognitive connection, would be upright posture, breathing air, experiencing pain, composition, social distance. Similarity bases provide a basis for humans to become empathetic towards other species. To give an example, if an animal has fallen down or a plant has drooped, we can assume that it is in an unnatural position and probably not doing well in that situation. Similarly, we interpret a bumblebee that has fallen into a water tank and is buzzing around as being in danger of drowning, based on the analogous relationship that we as land creatures have with water. If we offer the bumblebee a branch or a piece of paper, we have in fact performed a successful biotranslation.

Biotranslation could be used to find appropriate correspondences in human culture that represent animals and their umwelt structures. Biotranslation would consist of first locating the meanings and expressions of the animal in relation to its environment, based on the systemic analysis of the meaning structures (umwelt analysis). Then, as a second step, an analysis of the cultural languages, codes and narratives can be carried out in order to find suitable equivalents. In the case of the representation of other species, this would mean, firstly, searching for similarities between animal and human umwelts and, secondly, searching for suitable artistic expressions to convey the meanings in literary or artistic space.

Animal cultural representations based on semiotic modelling and biotranslation would help to bring the voice and interests of non-humans into NBS decision-making. Some examples are given in Section 5.4 and Appendix 5 (but also 3.3). When creating visualized representations of animal umwelts and affordances, several creative methods can be used: changing existing cultural codes, creating new models, changing scale, looking closely, taking the animal's position (e.g. subjectivity, reference to embodiment and bodily experiences), reframing, defamiliarizing, distorting, telling stories, using narratives, imagining futures (cf. Mossner 2017).

2. GENERAL METHODOLOGY OF UMWELT-BASED PLACE ANALYSIS

Umwelt-based place analysis is a qualitative research method that focuses on the most relevant aspects and features of a place from the basis of the research problem and by considering non-human species. It takes a biocentric view by including the perspective of different non-human species and paying attention to the environment as perceived by the animal. The main aim of the methodology is to make visible how different human participants and non-human species perceive specific environments ('umwelt analysis'), what meanings and significance given environments provide to them (analysing affordances, ecofields) in the context of challenges and possibilities of nature-based solutions.

The analysis combines different perspectives and levels of description: 1) defining the object and research problem; describing the area from the perspective of 2) key species' umwelts; 3) human activities; 4) the whole ecological community (see Appendix 2, 3). The analysis uses a number of data sources, which can be combined depending on the specifics of the Living Lab and the availability of the information. The main sources of input for the umwelt-based place analysis are 1) visits and observations in the area; 2) existing ecological reports, scientific knowledge and citizen science data (on biological species) as well as historical descriptions and visuals on the area and species; 3) results of the Coevolvers unified survey and interviews with experts; 4) results from data collected through participatory research methods: storytelling, walking interviews and photovoice. The analysis can draw on and combine the skills and insights of experts, amateur naturalists, and local people/stakeholders.

When engaging with the analysis, the following preliminary questions would be relevant to consider 1) How does the umwelt-based place analysis relate to your Living Labs research questions and goals? Which of the proposed methods do you think work best? 2) What kind of data sources could you use in your Living Lab? Who and how could collect the data / carry out the analysis? 3) Are there any issues or problems that you can think of when thinking about umwelt-based place analysis in the context of your Living Lab? The local research team can then proceed with data analysis and collection, followed by generalization and synthesis of findings, and visualization of affordances and multispecies participation (see sections 4 and 5 of this report).

2.1 A note on human umwelt

One key aspect of the umwelt analysis is the recognition of the researcher's own umwelt—it means, both the specifics of human perception, but also the cultural and social values and biases that shape human attitudes towards non-humans. This does not mean that the human perspective should be thereby extinguished from the analysis, but vice versa, by explicating the human perspective and being aware of its inevitable presence, one can determine the limits of accessing other umwelts, but at the same time show in the positive, how one's own umwelt not only inhibits the access,

but at the same time also creates the possibilities for connections. Such an awareness about the human perspective can also be put into practical use, when introducing non-human umwelts—for educational purposes to compare the other species umwelts with those of humans. Thereby the human perspective is explicated, yet it is rather used as a comparative tool to understand the specifics of non-human perspectives.

2.2 Four stages of the analysis

The analysis combines different perspectives and levels of description: 1) defining the object and research problem; describing the area from the perspective of 2) key species umwelts; 3) human activities; 4) the whole ecological community. The strength of the analyses lies in the combination and juxtaposition of these different perspectives. See Appendix 2 and 3 for details.

The first opening stage provides the basic description and understanding of the research object. This stage focuses on: 1) formulating the problems with the site and species that may require a solution; 2) determining the area to be described; 3) determining the key species which umwelt will be particularly focused.

The second stage highlights the subjective involvement, needs and perspectives of non-humans and provides information about what affordances in the environment are important to them. Specifically, the relationships between animal umwelts and environmental affordances (ecofields) should be made by considering four basic categories of meaning (functional cycles in Uexküll 2010). Mapping the biological needs and affordances of key species and deriving the key ecofields, affordances, relationships with other species and humans.

The third stage of the analysis provides an understanding of the human impact on the community and identifies specific ways in which human activities can conflict with non-humans, as well as mutually supportive relationships and co-creative potential. This stage should describe the main human activities that control and modify the ecosystem, its community and its key species, as well as human knowledge of non-human species, their activities that affect affordances for non-humans, and the relationships between human actors and non-human species.

The fourth stage provides an estimate of the overall communicative (i.e. semiotic) richness of the area. This can be done by focusing on the structural, ecological and semiotic (communicational) diversity of the area (beyond the key species and human relationships). It is suitable for finding core areas (more biodiverse and semiotically rich areas) and for comparing different places (e.g. for eco-social compensation). The description should focus on: 1) the spatial structure of the community; 2) the total number of different habitat types in the area; 3) the approximate age of the community; 4) the origin or evolution of the community. This part of the analysis could be understood as a description of the structure of the area (place as text).

2.3 Technical tools for data gathering

Umwelt-based analysis requires understanding 1) existing ecological conditions, 2) species living in the environment, and 3) environmental affordances. Information about

the (historical) development of specific ecosystems and different usages of the environment by humans now and in the past can also be useful. While sources for gathering of information vary by situation and location, the report provides a list of technical tools used for data gathering on umwelt analysis in LLs:

Umwelt cards – unified card deck to depict the characteristic animals in the area, provide information about their home range, movement abilities, activity period, primary senses, and relations to humans. Umwelt cards help imagine the differences of common species in NBS and perceive the location from different viewpoints considering perception and engagement of different animal species. Umwelt cards has been used in several NBS locations for explicating perspectives and needs of nonhuman species (see Appendix 1).

Photovoice – Photovoice is a method that uses photography and storytelling to reflect the physical conditions and experiences of participants. Photovoice participants take photos, for example with digital cameras or smartphones, and collect stories virtually through voice recording or sending messages. The collection of photos is followed by a live event where the photos and stories are shared and discussed. The photovoice method helps build shared understanding in the community and provides valuable data for analysis. If the theme of the photos is limited to a specific topic, such as animals, Photovoice can shed light on the role and involvement of non-human species in NBS. Photovoice was used for instance in LL launch events.

Walking interviews – They provide valuable info mainly because the environment itself serves as an interface or medium that motivates remembering, noticing, and interpreting. Walking interviews can be conducted with locals, experts, etc.

Observation – can give preliminary or basic information about the environment – what plant and animal species inhabit this, how people use this, etc. Information gathered through observations depends on the season, time of the day, etc., and is thus situative and subjective.

Umwelt awareness exercises – These are physical exercises that combines insights from mindfulness meditations and umwelt theories. The aim of the exercises is to shift the participants common mindset and attention and invite them to notice ways how non-human species relate with the NBS locations. The exercise is followed by group discussion. Umwelt awareness exercise is designed to be followed in small groups when visiting NBS sites (see section 3.2 for additional information).

Collecting local stories/ organizing storytelling events – Local stories can give valuable information about various species living in the area, environmental changes, people's engagements with the environment, etc. that might be inaccessible to scientific sources (see more on that in section 3.3).

Interviews with experts – Interviews follow the common social science methodology of semistructured qualitative interviews.

Citizen science applications, e.g. Naturenex – These applications enable gathering information about a wide range of ecological aspects that might be overlooked in scientific data collection. Naturenex application is currently under development (WP1 (Task 1.2)). It enables users to send information about themselves and their relation with the location, geographical coordinates, information about species encountered and their comments about wildlife and its living conditions as well as upload images.

3. UMWELT-BASED METHODS TAILORED TO LL NEEDS AND DERIVED EXPERIENCES

The general methodology of the umwelt-based place analysis was adapted and tailored to the specific needs and research interests of the Coevolvers project LLs. As umwelt methodology is relatively flexible and dynamic, it turned out to be suitable to use it in a variety of different NBS situations. In more detailed way, the umwelt approach was used in four LLs focusing on multispecies approaches: multispecies ecosocial compensation (Turku LL), mindfulness and making positive connections with the environment (Cagliari LL), building local community, and discovering multispecies environment through local stories and storytelling (Tartu LL), shepherding local ecosystem and developing digital nature tools (Murray LL). The consultations with LLs took place in the form of digital meetings, providing theoretical reflections on umwelt approach and non-humans, analysing, and giving feedback on interviews. Different research situations in LLs provided good information about the usability of the umwelt methodology in various contexts (see appendix 4).

3.1 Umwelts, affordances, and ecosocial compensation (Turku LL)

Turku Pansio-Perno LL focuses on the use of ecosocial compensation strategies. The LL area is heterogeneous with small hills, forest areas, coastal meadows, riverbanks, as well as different types of housing and inhabitants (including refugees), industries and harbours. The area has a very interesting history as a refugium of temperate deciduous forests but is now in a phase of active urban planning and future development (Turku 2024a). The aim of the Living Lab is to balance the urban development through NBS and, especially, ecosocial compensation strategies. As in Turku LL the focus is on a larger area, the proposals from the umwelt methodology also aim to consider affordances in the multi-species environment. It was proposed to:

1. describe and highlight multi-species community hotspots – areas that are particularly valuable for people and nature in a multi-species framework;
2. to include non-human species in ecosocial compensation strategies by including umwelt analysis – asking what kind of needs and resources key species need to thrive in the area;
3. organising the work in terms of time: historical (oak trees), currently used affordances (resting areas, sources of biodiversity) and affordances with future potential (opening of the coast).

Focusing on the multi-species affordances in the area, it was suggested to work on barriers (roads, hillets, river) and connectors (green belts) and to pay attention to how the area is situated in the wider geographical context. For example, the creation of a narrow green zone on the coastal bank across Ruissalo (biodiversity hotspot, see Turku 2024b) could significantly increase the accessibility of the Pansio-Perno for birds and other animals.

3.2 Umwelts, affordances, and mindfulness (Cagliari LL)

Cagliari LL is represented by the Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, which is a large lagoon near the city of Cagliari in Sardinia. It is a biodiversity hotspot, important for pink flamingos, other water birds, amphibians and reptiles, and is also a Ramsar site. At the same time, it is the location of economic interests, salt mining (not working at present) and various tourist activities (horticultural society, hiking, sports activities). The focus of the LL is to increase citizens' environmental knowledge, awareness, and education, particularly through the theoretical approach of environmental psychology. The LL activities aim at raising the awareness of humans towards non-humans, targeting also children and adolescents. The challenge is to combine human needs (tourist attractions, economy) with the needs of non-humans and to find new ways of relating to nature in Cagliari LL. As part of the Umwelt analysis, interviews were carried out with three specialists (two biologists, one economist) and the Umwelts of several bird species common to the area were analysed. Combining Cagliari LL's professional interests in environmental psychology and mindfulness practice, the following Umwelt awareness exercise was designed. The aim of the exercise is to shift perspectives and sensations to become aware of non-human others and their interactions with the environment. The method was tested in the LL place at the Coevolvers meeting in Cagliari on 23.04.2024.

Umwelt awareness exercise in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park

1. Walk around, look for a real existing animal (bird, insect, fish, etc) on the laguna. 5 minutes (or as long as possible/necessary)
2. Relax and observe the way they act (what they do, location, posture, style of movement, rhythm). 5 minutes (or as long as possible/necessary)
3. Imagine and think how they relate to the relevant inanimate nature (how they balance on the ground, grasp a branch, move in the water, jump, fly in the air etc). 5 minutes
4. Use your own body (or part of that – a hand) to imitate the movements of this animal. First, try to grasp the sense and sensation of the movement. Then focus on the touch and interaction with the inanimate nature – what sort of bodily sensations emerge and change. 10 minutes
5. Visualize the laguna as experienced from the perspective of the given animal – what they sense, what environmental features are relevant and necessary for them. How your own sensations, perceptions and understandings have broadened. 5 minutes
6. Try to verbalize the experience and share this with a partner or a group. 10 minutes

3.3 Local stories and storytelling as a source for knowing environmental affordances (Tartu LL)

The Living Lab in Tartu is focused on Ülejõe, Kvissentali, and Raadi regions in the North-West part of Tartu city. The area is fragmented and diverse by household types – there are older apartment buildings in the centre of the area in the Ülejõe

neighbourhood, a quiet older suburban area with big gardens around the cemetery in the Raadi neighbourhood, and new suburban areas along the river Emajõgi in Kvissentali neighbourhood and on the borders of Raadi. The area is also biologically diverse, containing a big old park area in Raadi cemetery, an old willow alley along Emajõgi, and river meadows around Kvissentali. The LL area serves as a buffer between the city and the rural area surrounding Tartu, thus green spaces there have become an important refuge and passageway for many wild species. At the same time, Ülejõe, Raadi, and Kvissentali regions in Tartu have undergone big changes in recent decades mainly because of new housing developments in Kvissentali and Raadi. Some new residential developments and a big infrastructure project of Tartu's northern bypass are yet to come.

In the context of these speedy developments, Tartu LL aims to discover a multispecies city, by providing tools and methodologies that make people acknowledge various non-human species and their needs and value in urban space. Considering the perspectives of non-human species in both everyday practices such as gardening and at the level of spatial planning enables buffering and managing rapid changes and compensating for the loss of natural habitats for various species. Discovering and “translating” umwelts of a diverse range of species in the area will serve as a fundamental base for the co-creation of adequate NBS in Tartu LL. To get to know the area and its inhabitants, the plan for collecting local environment-related narratives was established for Tartu LL.

Local narratives (or eco-narratives, geographical lore, place-lore) express the characteristics of the specific environment and people's engagements with their surroundings and non-human beings. Local narratives related to urban nature can be, for example, personal stories or family folklore about creating a garden, meeting different species, etc., or more well-known stories about cultural or natural heritage or important locations in the area. Environmental characteristics or ecological actors are usually at the center of these kinds of local and contextual stories. Local place-related stories enable understanding affordances in specific environments, as they express what environment provides for various people or communities, and non-human species. In addition, local narratives are also a relevant source of information and therefore part of the umwelt-based place analysis explained in section 2. Often, the information about how the local ecosystem has developed, what species are found there or visit the environment, and what environmental changes have taken place cannot be known through nature science or citizen science data but can be accessed through memories of people from the area.

The focus of collecting the local stories is two-fold: how people engage with urban nature and its affordances, and also how they engage with other species. Narratives make biotranslation (see more Kull, Torop 2003) possible and are sometimes the result of successful biotranslation. The activity of different species or inter- and intraspecies communication is described in local narratives. Moreover, narratives can describe experiences and emotions that both human and non-human inhabitants understand, such as struggles of access, meeting barriers, and disconnections when moving around. Acknowledging similar struggles and similar usages of urban greenery can create empathy towards non-human species.

Storytelling method has been discussed in Coevolvers LL meetings and other events within Tartu LL. While narratives can make non-human umwelts accessible and create empathy, they also manifest the existing anthropocentrism. As narratives express our human umwelts and our limited capabilities of creating semiotic relations, some species like big mammals or predatory species have a greater role in narratives than the ones hard to see or perceive by humans. This must be considered when integrating local stories into LL activities.

In addition to studying local affordances and making umwelts accessible, storytelling events and sharing the stories collected can tighten relationships and communication inside communities. One of the practical challenges that Tartu LL faces when planning its activities is social fragmentation in areas and the lack of pre-existing local communities or communication mediums. Raadi, Kvissentali, and Ülejõe provide very different kinds of urban experiences and facilitate various kinds of households and lifestyles. Stories that bring environmental engagements in the centre, can create common ground for supporting non-human species in urban environments and developing NBS.

For collecting local stories in Tartu LL regions, three simple questions were provided, and these will be distributed with the request among local people and people related to the regions (through work, leisure, various activities, etc). The questions proposed were the following:

Please share some stories with us:

About a place in Ülejõe, Kvissental, or Raadi that is significant/important to you (whether in a good or a bad way). Where is this place located? Why is it important?

About a memorable encounter with an animal (mammal, bird, insect, fish, reptile, etc.) around your home.

About your neighbours of other species, such as plants, animals, insects, etc., that you encounter daily.

Questions were piloted in the Coevolvers Budapest meeting in a storytelling workshop and in the workshop held in the Estonian Literary Museum, Estonian Folklore Archive in Tartu (by Riin Magnus and Lona Päll). Questions were tested in various garden visits in Tartu. The Tartu LL team will share the requests and questions through our e-mail list for the core group and in various social media channels. In addition, some storytelling events for locals will be organized.

3.4 Do plants count – umwelts and affordances for the ecosystem (Murray LL).

The Living Lab in Murray Park, Scotland, UK focuses on the management of community-owned woodlands by local people, deepening human-nature connections, enhancing local biodiversity and community resilience through woodland care and stewardship. The LL also focuses on the development of digital tools for nature education (Virtual Nature tool). From an ecological perspective, Woodland Park is a diverse woodland ecosystem with low human influence. Consultations with Murray Living Lab have focused on two issues: (1) the inclusion of non-human animal

perspectives in the Virtual Nature tool. (2) the possibility of including plant species (trees), fungi, mosses and other 'non-animal' species in the umwelt analysis, and In the first issue of incorporating non-human perspectives into virtual representations, simple methods would include modifying viewpoint and perspective, modifying temporality (time-lapse), marking elements that are meaningful to key species through digital editing (colouring). Incorporating the perspectives of keystone species into virtual representations of nature will enhance our understanding of forests as a multi-species community and improve our ability to perceive the role and needs of other species with which we share ecosystems.

The second issue of including "non-animals" relates to the question of how to apply an umwelt-based place analysis in complex ecosystems – here it is most appropriate to focus on the 4th stage of the analysis "the whole ecological community", which describes the structure of the ecosystem. The role of sessile life forms can also be derived from the 2nd stage of analysis "the umwelts of key species" as a shared affordance in their umwelts. In relevant cases, trees and other sessile living forms can also be treated as key species in the analysis.

In the context of applying the analysis to the whole ecosystem, Murray Living Lab was also consulted on the issue of coding the material (interviews, textual representations) using keywords that reflect umwelts approach. The following list of keywords was provided:

- (functional) relationship between humans and animals or between animals;
- affordance (a property of a place that makes a certain activity or behaviour possible, for human or non-human species);
- bridge, connection;
- companion, partner (including human, non-human, cross-species);
- conflict (direct, symbolic or over environmental uses);
- absence, lack of something needed;
- obstacle, barrier.

4. SEMIOTIC MODELLING AND ANALYSIS

Gathering and combining different sources of information, as described in the methodology of umwelt-based place analysis, provides an overview of multi-species interactions in the given Living Labs. Generalizing and analysing the data allows specific incompatibilities between human and non-human participants and in relation to environmental affordances to be identified. By suggesting new types of interactions and affordances to be used, the analysis can indicate co-creation opportunities and potentials for nature-based solutions. At the same time, the results presented in this section are preliminary for specific Living Labs of the project as well as for general readers. The mapping of co-creation opportunities and suggestions for improving nature-based solutions should continue in parallel with other activities throughout the life cycle of this project.

4.1 Identifying and deducing conflicts in needs, meanings and values

In a multi-species setting, incompatibilities and even conflicts in needs, meanings and values are common. From the ecofield perspective, the most common sources of such conflicts are: (1) irreconcilable differences between umwelts, (2) conflicting uses of affordances or environmental resources, (3) lack of competence or knowledge in nonhumans (about changing environments), (4) lack of affordances themselves, habitat or environmental resources. Additional sources of conflict for non-humans may include (5) the appearance of invasive species, or (6) environmental change on a local or global scale (deforestation, effects of climate change). For human stakeholders, sources of conflict may also include differences in (7) knowledge and understanding of non-human species and ecosystems, (8) aesthetic preferences, (9) habits, practices and uses of the environment, (10) worldviews and value hierarchies.

These different sources of conflict can combine in a variety of configurations between different levels of complexity. For example, in Tartu and Turku LL the potential conflict between human aesthetic preference for open coastlines and riverbanks and the need of many other species for closed waterfronts covered by vegetation could be identified. Another common source of conflict seems to be between business interests and valuation of infrastructure development, and the needs of human inhabitants for a rich living environment and access to nature (Cagliari LL). In Hutton LL, conflictual affordances were described due to predatory ecological relationships (pine martens and red squirrels, red and grey squirrels, mink and ducks and voles) and between humans and non-humans (with deer due to damage to young trees and with badgers due to setts on agricultural land). It is suggested that conflicts based on ecological relationships cannot be eliminated, but the presence of diverse landscapes with many habitats, resources and opportunities helps to reduce conflicts.

The different causes of conflict form a matrix that influences the situation in Living Lab sites. At the same time, such a matrix can be used as a basis for analysis and also to suggest ways of solving the conflicts. While working with conflicts of needs, meanings

and values, we also need to take into account their inequality and issues of environmental justice – participants do not have equal capacity to express their position. For example, the analysis might weight meanings, values and needs in terms of livelihood needs (as critical for survival, beneficial for well-being, choice of taste or preference, etc.). Combining this with the capacity of each stakeholder group to express their interests would lead to a more balanced representation.

4.2 Absence of affordances

For the analysis of multi-species environments in nature-based solutions, affordances are considered as macro-level phenomena, as general properties of the environment that enable or prevent life for the number of species and also act as a ground for regulating the relations between species. Absence of affordances indicates a situation where the site could support a greater number of species or their relationships, but this is not the case due to the lack of some resource property.

Absence of affordances may relate to specific needs, meanings or values of the human or non-human participants, or it may be more general, derived from the patterns and structures of the ecosystem. Here we can discover different motifs of meanings of the environment that form the specific configuration: “There can be a number of different motifs in the environment and motifs can make supporting, contrasting, or conflicting interactions with one another. Analysis of patterns and motifs can reveal focal points of meaning or hidden tensions (e.g. ‘dissent’ as an environmental counterforce to cultural discourse, Low 2008) of the given environment, as well as ‘absentia’, that is, meaning-complexes that are expected to be present in a given environment but are missing for some reason.” (Maran 2020a: 67).

Methodologically, there appear to be two main ways of identifying missing affordances: (1) look at the matrix of different umwelts (general analysis, stage two) and find out which life functions are not fulfilled for the number of species due to the lack of some environmental feature or property; (2) make a comparison between similar places (or follow the historical development of the place) and identify the missing or non-functional affordances.

Examples of common affordances are: (1) access to drinking water; (2) forest area providing habitat and resources for the number of species; (3) multifunctional community gardens; (4) routes for movement and migration; (5) safety/rest areas for human/non-human participants. The common affordance of almost all Living Labs is access to nature for human participants and opportunities for interspecies contact. Examples of a few missing affordances identified in the analyses include: (1) lack of connectivity and access between different green areas (Tartu LL, Turku LL, Barcelona LL); (2) lack of large trees in the vicinity providing nesting places (Tartu LL, Kvissentali flooded meadow); (3) lack of community centre that would enable community self-organisation (Tartu LL, Turku LL); (4) lack of knowledge about the role of non-humans and nature-based solutions in governance (Budapest LL) or in the general public (Barcelona LL).

4.3 Co-creation opportunities and potentials for NBS

In suggesting co-creation opportunities and potentials, it is important to understand that for most non-human species, humans are the primary cause of degradation of habitats and living resources. Therefore, the first consideration should be to assess our planned activities for potential harm and look for solutions that require less energy, action or change.

One way of working with conflicts, lack of affordances and co-creation potential would be to look for points of existing common interests between different stakeholders. There are examples from Living Labs of such common ground – such as the need for fire protection (in Barcelona LL) or the ability of forests to store water (in Beskydy LL). A similar function can be seen in ecological keystone or umbrella species, which have the potential to represent the interests of a variety of non-humans and also to consolidate different cultural understandings (red flamingo in Cagliari LL, penduline tit in Tartu LL in Kvissentali). The analysis also needs to take into account that not all affordances need to be physical. For example, in Hutton LL the mental/spiritual affordance was described as the park was valued by the community and recognized as a 'magical place' associated with a sense of wellbeing and belonging. Such mental/spiritual affordances may operate as “umbrella affordance” that have a potential for establishing common ground between different participants and their interests.

There are also examples in the observed LL where one participant (species or group thereof) provides affordances for another participant – in Budapest LL bird nests and bird houses have relaxing and aesthetic function for hospital patients, in Tartu LL multifunctional private gardens provide resources for both human and non-human needs. Similarly, the concept of the Wildfire Eaters in Barcelona LL is based on interlocking affordances and needs between humans and non-humans. Such already existing interconnections provide an important starting point and model for developing co-creation opportunities and potentials in Living Labs.

We can use the above matrix (Section 4.1) of different meanings and values and the remarks about the lack of affordances as a starting point for searching for co-creation potentials. The key question here is to find ways to connect existing needs, meanings and activities between different human and non-human actors. What new affordances could connect different participants and create novel configurations would include feedback that is thus self-supporting and resilient. For example, human aesthetic preferences and desires for the colours, sounds and movements of non-human species could be linked to practical activities that secure habitat and resources for non-humans (Herrmann-Pillath et al. 2023). This could be achieved, for example, by linking opportunities to experience wildlife with activities such as rewilding, composting and cleaning. As another example of such a link, the idea of a sanctuary or refuge could be extended to a multi-species setting by creating green 'safe areas' for both human and non-human residents. The aim of such urban sanctuaries would be to create specific zones free from fear and stress for both human and non-human participants. Working with co-creation opportunities and potentials for NBS in this way predictably brings with it a shift in meaning and values towards multispecies inclusivity and connectivity.

5. POSSIBILITIES FOR VISUALISING UMWELTS AND AFFORDANCES FOR HUMAN DECISION-MAKING

Second major goal of the current report is to find effective methods and strategies for communicating affordances and non-human needs to governance and policy practices related to nature-based solutions. The premise of this task is to understand that non-humans are systematically underrepresented in human social and political processes. From the perspective of human decision-making, non-humans can be interpreted as a vulnerable, unheard minority. Including interests and needs of nonhumans into NBS decision-making would enable noticing and accessing previously concealed affordances. This would make NBS richer and more diverse and unlock co-creative developmental potential. Underrepresentation of non-humans can be effectively tackled by combining results of the umwelt analysis and previously gathered knowledge of non-human affordances with creating artistic and cultural representations. We suggest that semiotic modelling, which allows knowledge to be transferred between different registers, codes, and cultural languages, can be effectively applied in this process. The starting point for this translation is knowledge about non-human species, their needs, place relations and interactions with humans, derived from the umwelt-based place analysis (section 2). As humans tend to value highly cultural works and artefacts – poems, paintings, sculptures, films – we observe the possibility of using cultural creation and cultural texts as a model for valuing non-human others for human decision-making. Visual and narrative structures can be seen as methods to increase the value of hidden affordances and to empower non-humans in nature-based solutions.

We apply principles of semiotic modelling and biotranslation (section 1.4) to explore different ways of making this transfer and expressing non-human needs. These include short technical guidelines that are familiar and easily applicable to policy makers. Another option, storytelling is highly receptive to local specificities and local species in LL and contributes to community building, while map-based representations integrate well with technical data collection tools and existing GIS databases. Non-human letters and affordance visualisation draw on existing literary and artistic genres, making them both intuitively usable and effective for upscaling non-humans. The described methods have been used in LL in various combinations (non-human letters – Tartu LL, Beskydy LL; storytelling – Turku LL, Tartu LL). The choice between the proposed methods should depend on the social format or occasion (community meeting, landscape planning discussion, meeting with the local council, etc.) and the proposed methods could be combined or synthesized.

5.1 Short technical guidelines

When communicating with municipal officials or political representatives, information about affordances and non-humans can be presented in short technical guidelines. This is a form of communication that is familiar and often expected by professionals and can therefore serve as a starting point for considering alternatives. The advantage of short technical guidelines is that they are practical and focused and can be easily adapted to decision-making and management. At the same time, such technical communication obscures the agency of human and non-human stakeholders and does not well represent the complexity of relationships in Living Labs, nor their co-evolutionary potential. As part of the current analysis, it could be suggested that the guidelines be directly and sufficiently grounded in the results of the umwelt-based place analysis. As an example of the guidelines, the excerpt from the short report of Tartu LL (5 April 2024) to the city authorities of Tartu is presented:

- “- Planning should include a communal area. There should be green spaces of at least one block in size, to be included in the zoning of the area.
- Landscaping and storm water drainage ditches are nature friendly. Artificial recreational facilities have been created, but nature as a recreational resource has been reduced. Ensure that the floodplain is maintained as an area of natural beauty close to the city.
- The riverside area is not accessible all year round. There is no convenient path along the river, e.g. no way to get there with a pushchair. Bridges and access should be provided for better access.”

5.2 Building common ground by sharing stories

Using narratives to make sense of surroundings and other beings is essentially human, thus, the narrative approach has become popular in environmental communication and nature management. It is possible to create and use narratives in environmental management or communication to make sense of other species or illustrate their struggles and needs (for example narratives performed in puppet theatre by KIDO Foundation, one of the overseas cousins in the Coevolvers project). In other cases, we can rely on existing local narratives that individuals and communities share and that focus on the environment. Hereby, we concentrate on the latter and explain how to use local narratives as input for policymakers (see also an example of collecting narratives in Tartu LL in section 3.3).

Supporting biodiverse urban environments and creating NBS that consider various species requires understanding non-human animals' umwelts. i.e. how they perceive, use, and change environment. Local narratives about engagements with environment and other species can give an additional medium or tool for acknowledging and describing non-human umwelts. Storytelling enables mediating, explaining, translating, and through that, giving access to non-human umwelts. This is possible because narratives can create empathy through shared experiences of the environment (see more in section 3.3). Narratives can also describe ecofields and thus help to map out possible conflicts over resources and space. Often local stories describe how different species use the environment (e.g. people grow flowers and vegetables in gardens, water voles inhabit gardens for food); where and when people

and non-human species meet (e.g. parks are leisure areas for people and passageways for small mammals); what parts of environment people or other species use and what parts they ignore (e.g. areas with intensive traffic are ignored by various groups of people and animals), etc. These kinds of connections and counterpoints are highly relevant to consider in governance and policy practices.

While narratives are valuable for illustrating affordances for people and non-humans and considering non-humans' umwelts, local stories themselves are not easily usable in governance or transferrable for policymakers. In fact, local stories are artistic, creative interpretations, sometimes long, sometimes personal and dealing with micro-level of the environment while policymakers need to work with the complex systems. We have mapped out some ways of how to “translate” gathered narratives in a way they could serve as input for policymaking:

(1) *Providing additional data or context to local stories can be valuable for policymakers.* By contextualizing stories within schemas, timelines, or spatial frameworks (e.g. presenting local place-related stories on a map), it becomes easier to integrate these narratives into spatial management or planning. This approach can inform development plans, the construction of new infrastructure, the creation of nature protection areas, green spaces, and more.

(2) *Using data or text analysis methodologies to analyse stories enables the creating of a more systemized, organized, and focused input.* For example, by using keywords and coding the texts, it becomes possible to identify which species are present in the narratives and which affordances, functions, or resources are most frequently mentioned and thus considered more relevant.

(3) *Using storytelling as a method motivates dialogue between values, meanings, and concerns related to environment and non-human species.* Policy practices and governance are part of the narrative realm. By utilizing storytelling practices and organizing storytelling events, it becomes possible to uncover policymakers' own narratives and set them in dialogue with those of the locals. For instance, certain plant or animal species or gardening practices may be viewed negatively from a policy perspective, while locals may have emotional connections and practices related to these. Focusing on narratives enables sharing different experiences, viewpoints, and visions without confronting, challenging, or negotiating these directly.

(4) *Sharing stories can be seen as an additional tool for public participation or discussions in governance.* For example, in addition to (or before) organising public participation events where different groups can discuss their thoughts, one can organise fieldwork to collect local stories, field trips, storytelling events, etc. In these events, people can discuss their engagement with the environment as well as concerns related to changes in that environment.

5.3 Map-based representations

Map-based representations are effective for communicating non-human needs and NBS to policy-makers because it is a dominant tool in planning practices, therefore easily understandable and useable by policy-makers and in the context of governance. NBSs are often dependent on geographical space, mapping helps in their planning

and assessing the scale of impact. Providing a universal spatial framework, cartography and GIS help to turn notes from interviews or fieldwork into geographically positioned data. Mapping locates the data by limited tools of either points of location, lines of movement, spread or distance and areas. This wide and relatively simple use, apparent objectivity and universal translatability is also a crucial restriction. First using the most common tool of representation in planning can restrict ability to think outside of daily tasks, known problems and habitual solutions as ‘medium is the message’. Second, mapping can include a huge variety of using spatial relations to depict something and map-based representation is therefore an open field of creative solutions that do not fit with GIS coordinates. For example, cognitive mapping of subjective worlds in humans or mapping the environmental perception of non-humans visiting a place.

In general, maps can locate humans and non-humans, environmental affordances, encounters, conflicts, processes, and various relations (potentially) present in an area. From the perspective of umwelt analysis:

- (1) maps can locate the actual or potential presence of particular non-humans and areas relevant to them in a wider region;
- (2) environmental affordances and functional space in a restricted place as relevant to chosen species can be located by mapping;
- (3) interrelating relevant places for several species, multi-species relevance and density can be mapped;
- (4) through cognitive mapping of an area for a particular species or organism, maps can depict subjective worlds, while this not congruent with GIS, this invites the consideration of meanings of the environment from human and non-human perspectives, creative and co-creative methods and qualitative methods in more general.

5.4 Visualized short narratives

To represent non-humans, their umwelts and affordances in the context of NBS, we propose to use methods of cultural representation (deriving from umwelt analysis and biotranslation). Literary narratives and images are often seen in culture as a valued form of communication that can also be used to valorise and empower non-humans. Culturally filtered and gentrified insights can be used to highlight the subjective perspectives and interests of non-humans and later translated back into political and technical decision-making (landscape design, NBS policies). More specifically we suggest using: 1) short first-person narratives called “nonhuman letters” to express nonhuman experiences, umwelts, and ecofields; 2) artistic mosaic-like representations of the given place or landscape to visualize the multispecies perspectives on affordances.

Non-human letters – visualized short narratives. Citizen letters are well-known and familiar form of communication to municipal officials and planners. Here, we develop this format to make visible non-humans, their umwelt, affordances, needs and fears. Nonhuman letters use a literary creative approach but are strictly based on previous umwelt analysis and other data sources. They should be taken as translations from an

animal perspective that serve the function to represent interests of nonhumans (see Appendix 5).

Guidelines for writing non-human letters are following:

- 1) Keep the letter short, use simple sentences and clear language.
- 2) Write in the first person, starting with the sentence "I am" (species name).
- 3) Be data driven by using umwelt analysis and other information sources.
- 4) Cover the following topics: living place, needs/requirements, essential affordances, importance to ecosystem and community, potential conflicts, dangers/fears.
- 5) Use creative language but avoid poetic exaggerations and anthropomorphizing.
- 6) Be self-reflective by considering from what position and with what emphasise are you writing.

Affordance mosaics – visualisation of affordances. Affordances for different human and non-human stakeholders can be visualised by the artist as images representing the general landscape of the NBS site, stakeholders and site characteristics relevant to different groups. Such images are inspired by Jakob von Uexküll's (2010) depictions of the environment as meaningful to different species. The key feature of the image is the rearrangement of depicted landscape elements according to their relevance to selected species. Changing the scale, enlarging relevant elements and using mosaic-like display can also be used to represent affordances for different participants.

The example provided, drawn by Artur Kuus, is based on the information gained from the umwelt-based place analysis of Tartu LL, and represents the landscape as meaningful to three species: humans (recreational fishermen), beavers and penduline tit (see Appendix 5). Such visual representations provide an intuitive and immediate understanding of the NBS site as perceived by different species. The image helps to assess the role and needs of non-human species in the NBS. The number of species depicted could be increased and the visualisation combined with non-human letters.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a strong connection between affordance and NBS, as both are actualised for participating subjects as possibilities (for something). In a multi-species setting, NBS involves affordances for a variety of participants who are substantially different and have different perceptions and needs. Umwelt analysis, ecofield model and biotranslation are effective conceptual tools to study the perceivable role of non-humans in NBS. These resulted in the general methodology of umwelt-based place analysis, which was fruitfully tested in Coevolvers LL. The diversity of LL settings also enabled the development of umwelt-based methodology for specific needs, which can be seen as examples of how to adapt the method for different NBS. The analysis led to the identification of some meaning conflicts, missing affordances and co-evolution potentials for NBS. An important part of the task was the application of semiotic modelling to find the most appropriate cultural expressions. The visualisation of affordances is essential for NBS as it makes hidden affordances visible and increases their cultural value. As affordances are points of future development potential for NBS, affordance visualisation should be used and fed back into human decision making and design of NBS. The future steps of the task are working out digital data gathering tools, consulting LL in applying umwelt methods and providing input of nonhuman representations to NBS governance.

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APPENDIX 1. UMWELT CARDS AS TOOL FOR IMAGINATION

Photo: Gilles San Martin, [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Myotis_mystacinus_\(2863144030\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Myotis_mystacinus_(2863144030).jpg)

Whiskered bat. *Myotis mystacinus*

Home, nesting, or resting place: old buildings with open attics, tree cavities, hibernates in cellars and ruins. Feeds in mixed forest with clearings.

Movement: flying, local species but may do short-distance migrations (150 km).

Activity period: hibernates, active only in summer (spring, fall) and in night and twilight.

Primary senses: hearing, navigates by ultrasound.

Relation to humans: urban adapter, sleeps in human-built structures.

Photo: Shirokko-Shari, commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Vulpes_vulpes_laying_in_snow.jpg

Red fox. *Vulpes vulpes*

Home, nesting, or resting place: Burrows in sand or soil, usually on hillsides, open landscapes for feeding.

Movement: territorial species, very mobile (in urban areas living range is few hectares, in wild up to 100 hectares).

Activity period: active in night and day, and all around the year.

Primary senses: smell, hearing.

Relation to humans: urban exploiter, inhabits suburban landscapes, may eat on trash sites.

Photo: Korall, https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Rana_arvalis_in_Lil-Jansskogen_17.JPG

Moor frog. *Rana arvalis*

Home, nesting, or resting place: wetlands, riversides, deciduous forests.

Movement: very slowly on land, very sedentary species (range 100 meters).

Activity period: active in night and day and only in summer (hibernates).

Primary senses: hearing, sight.

Relation to humans: habitat overlap, threatened by car traffic and pollution.

Photo: Bengt Nyman, https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/R/Ba/Larus_argentatus

Herring gull. *Larus argentatus*

Home, nesting, or resting place: Flat roofs of buildings, nests in colonies, also on the seashore and islands.

Movement: flies, may cover 5-10 km in feeding flights.

Activity period: active only in daytime; mostly migratory bird (present in summer).

Primary senses: hearing, vision.

Relation to humans: urban exploiter, nests on human-built structures, and may feed in garbage dumps.

APPENDIX 2. THE UMWELT-BASED PLACE ANALYSIS

Contents

Introductory notes

Why to use umwelt-based analysis

Definitions of used concepts

Analysis:

I. Delimiting and describing the object

II. From the perspective of umwelts of key species

III. From the perspective of human activity

IV. From the perspective of the whole community

References

Additional sources

Table 1. Sample analysis from the perspective of umwelts of key species. Tartu Kvisentali Flooded Meadow

Table 2. Suggested sources of information and data

Appendix 1. Sample questions for discussion with the experts

Introductory notes

The analysis combines different viewpoints and levels of description: 1) determining the object and research problem; describing the area from the perspective of 2) umwelts of key species; 3) of human activity; 4) the whole ecological community. The strength of the analyses lies in combining and juxtaposing these different perspectives. The analysis uses a number of data sources that can be combined depending on the specifics of the Living Lab and availability of the information. Main sources to get input for umwelt analysis are: 1) visits and observations to the area; 2) already existing ecological reports, scientific knowledge and citizen science data (on biological species); 3) results of the Coevolvers unified questionnaire and interviews with experts (see Appendix 1: Sample questions for discussion with the experts); 4) storytelling, walking interviews and photovoice. Rely on two or three primary methods or data sources that suit best for you living lab (for more information, please see Table 2.)

The analysis can draw on and combine the skills and insights of biologists, amateur naturalists and local people/stakeholders. Completing Task 4 (see below) would require some experience in describing ecosystems and biotopes, while Tasks 1 and 2 can be completed in Living Labs with the help of local nature enthusiasts. Task 3 relies mainly on the experience of the lay people in the Living Labs. The analysis can also use preexisting data and other ongoing activities in the Living Labs. It is suggested to select the object and research problem based on preexisting information (Task 1), while other Tasks rely mostly on onsite analysis and observations.

Taking into account the specific research problem, the umwelt-based analysis should cover one full year. For this aim, it would be good to visit the site, observe the changes and interactions in different seasons.

Why to use umwelt-based analysis

The umwelt analysis is an efficient qualitative research method that focuses from the bases of research problem and by considering nonhuman species on most relevant aspects and features of a place, environment or situation. It takes a biocentric view (Martinelli 2010) by including the perspective of various nonhuman species and paying attention to the environment as perceived from the animal.

Definitions of used concepts

Affordances – The affordances of the environment are what it offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes, either for good or ill. (Gibson 1979). The property or quality of the environment for its inhabitants.

Community is the whole complex of living beings on the area of observation.

Ecofield – Every living function performed by organisms is associated with a specific spatial configuration of their surroundings, and the term 'eco-field' represents this configuration. The eco-field has been considered like an ecological space, or carrier of meaning, in which every living function interacts semiotically with the surrounding world (Farina, Belgrano 2006)

Functional cycle – The cyclic connection between parts of the environment (object), its perception, interpretation by an organism (subject) and its behavioral activity (or action) towards the object.

Habitat (biotope) – relatively homogenous area with steady environmental parameters (geographical relief, temperature, moisture) and stable composition of planta and animal species.

Key species are the species that have a significant role in obtaining the structure of the community or/and are specially relevant for the given research focus.

Umwelt is the personal environment of an agent [organism]; a set of meaningful distinctions and correspondences from an agent's perspective (Uexküll 1982).

Umwelt-net is the network of organisms' meaningful relations and communications in the local ecosystem.

Analysis

Task 1 creates the basic description and understanding of the research object.

The suggested information sources are: research agendas in Living Labs, live observations in the area, maps and existing environmental reports, scientific and popular literature of the species, citizen science databases, interviews with experts, walking interviews, storytelling (local narratives from the area).

I. Delimiting and describing the object. At first:

1.1. Formulate the problems with the site and species that may require a solution. Like population increase/decrease, relations with humans, effects on other species, anthropogenic species (the specific course of analysis could follow, e.g. conflict management could focus on 2,3, rising awareness 2,3, while increasing biodiversity and ecosocial compensation could put emphasis on 3,4).

1.2. Determine the area under description (see Maran 2020).

Create a short geophysical description of the area (waterways, type of climate, inland/costal area, as this gives basis for both available species and general affordances, type of community or ecosystem). The distinction between: anthropogenic, seminatural, natural, and restored areas can be made (see Kull 1998).

1.3. Determine the key species which umwelt will be of special focus e.g., from the perspective of ecological, cultural, economic (hunting) value or species protection.

For each selected species, provide a short description of their ecological role and place in the community (like herbivore, in the soil), abundance, stability, temporal presence (like migrating species, active in night).

II. From the perspective of umwelts of key species

Task two highlights the subjective involvement, needs and perspectives of non-humans and provides information of what affordances in the environment are important for them.

The sources of information could be: live observations in the area, citizen science databases, umwelt theory, scientific and popular literature on the species, maps and existing environmental reports, photographs (photovoice) made in the area, results of the expert interviews.

2.1. Make an analysis of the relations of animal umwelts and environmental affordances (ecofields). For this describe environment by taking into account four basic categories of meaning (basic functional cycles in Uexküll 1982: a) physical environment, b) predators and parasites, c) breeding, social partners and symbionts, d) food and resources).

In justified cases (significant cultural value) also plant species can be taken as key species to be analysed. In other occasions role of the plants comes out in a summary of the analysis through their interactions with other species.

2.2. The analysis can be compiled as a table (see the example: Table 1. Sample analysis from the perspective of umwelts of key species. Tartu Kvissentali Flooded Meadow).

2.3. Based on descriptions, deduce:

the main ecofields of the species (e.g. foraging EF, nesting EF, guarding EF, mobility EF, recreational EF),

the affordances provided in the site for the species (higher spruces enabling nesting, fence blocking the movement etc., also negative affordances),

their communicative and ecological relations with another species (umwelt-nets),

their communicative and ecological relations and conflicts with humans.

III. From the perspective of human activity

The task three provides understanding of the human impact to the community and points out specific ways how human activity can be conflictive with non-humans as well as points out mutually supportive relations and co-creative potentials.

The sources of information could be: live observations in the area, photographs (photovoice) made in the area, results of the questionnaire (WP4), interviews with experts, walking interviews, storytelling (local narratives from the area).

3.1. Main human activities in controlling and modifying the ecosystem, its community and its key species – this points to the functional relations between humans and other species in the area.

Human effects can be distinguished and described as following:

- mild / severe; single/occasional/regular;
- supportive/hindering, local/global (effects of climate change);
- individual/community-based/industrial;
- direct / indirect (through regulations and modifying environment).

3.2. The topic can be functionally specified and described as follows: In what ways the area and its nonhuman inhabitants are known, relevant and valued by the humans? By what activities and practices humans create, modify, or reduce affordances for non-human species? What general affordances (e.g., access to water, movement routes, obstacles) that are important to other species human activity creates or reduces? Are the key species related to any groupings or conflicts taking place between the human stakeholders?

IV. From the perspective of the whole community

Task number four provides an estimation of overall communicational (i.e. semiotic) richness of the area. This can be done focusing on the structural, ecological and semiotic (communicational) diversity of the area (beyond the key species and human relations). It is suitable for finding core areas (more biodiverse and semiotically rich areas) and comparing different places (e.g. for the eco-social compensation).

The sources of information could be: live observations in the area, existing environmental reports, photographs (photovoice) made in the area, scientific and popular literature about the species, citizen science databases, interviews with experts, storytelling (local narratives from the area)

4.1. Spatial structure of the community (vertical – the main layers: grass, bushes, undergrowth, trees; horizontal – the main habitat types, their homogeneity and mosaicism). Both the vertical and spatial structure are dependent on the scale of description; for the sake of simplicity we suggest to use the scale that is perceivable for human without technical equipment.

In the analysis count the total number of different habitat types in the area. Thereafter describe the spatial arrangement (size and shape) of individual habitat patches. Try to estimate, how simple or complex the arrangement of habitat is. The number and composition of different layers and patches gives a general estimate about the number of niches and affordances for non-humans.

4.2. The approximate age of the community (after the major disturbance, or creation of the green area, or rebuilding of the area, or forest fire, etc.). The possible distinctions could be following:

- novel (all new species, no steady relations),
- intermediate (some functional relations between species),
- well-established (high diversity, heterogeneity and patchiness),

saturated (rich in relations, but little dynamics and change).

Such description gives an estimate to the saturation level of the umwelt-net (because the network's saturation grows in time) and its stability.

4.3. Nativity of the community. The proportion and role of non-native species or domestic species – their involvement and effect in the community. Describe the relations between key species and nonnative or domestic species. This gives information about the stability of the community and its umwelt-net as well as potential problems.

Table 2. Suggested sources of information and data

	1.1	1.2	1.3	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	3.2	4.1	4.2	4.3
	The area			Key species			Human activities		Whole community		
<i>Live observations in the area</i>	*	*				*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Maps and existing environmental reports</i>	*	*	*		*	*			*	*	
<i>Scientific and popular literature of the species</i>			*	*	*						*
<i>Citizen science databases</i>			*	*							*
<i>Umwelt theory</i>					*						
<i>Photographs (photovoice) made in the area</i>					*	*	*	*	*	*	
<i>Results of the questionnaire (WP4.1)</i>							*	*			
<i>Results of the interviews with experts</i>	*			*		*	*	*			*
<i>Walking interviews</i>			*				*	*			
<i>Storytelling (local narratives from the area)</i>			*					*		*	*

Sample questions for discussion with the experts

1) How other (non-human) species are relevant for your Living Lab? What species are most noticeable / discussed? Are there any endangered or invasive species? Are trees/plants, fungi, or ecosystem (as a whole) also important for the given LL?

2) How humans relate to the species previously mentioned? How humans in general meet or become aware of other species?

3) What are the main resources or living opportunities (affordances) that the given area or Living Lab provides to other species?

4) Are there any issues or problems in including other (non-human) species to Nature-based Solutions / Living Lab. Are there any ethical dilemmas, that are related to including other species to Living Lab activities or interventions?

- 5) What sort of knowledge would you need to include other species better or to take their interests into account? What kind of umwelt-based activities could be used to include other species better?
- 6) How you see Living Lab activities and interventions influencing other species? Any there any species who are supported or repressed because of LL activities. For instance, how species composition is changed (balance of indigenous/anthropophilic/invasive species)?
- 7) Based on the discussion, would you like to use umwelt-based methods in your Living Lab in future?

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APPENDIX 3. ANALYSIS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF UMWELTS OF KEY SPECIES IN TARTU LL

Sample analysis of the Tartu Kvissentali Flooded Meadow, 18-19.10.2023

<https://maps.app.goo.gl/y4GQMrX3i2bY57eR6>

Species searches: I-naturalist, pluto F, E-elurikkus (selected species for which there were several reports from the Kvissentali flooded meadow, that were typical to the environment, also considering the representation of different taxa).

Species / functional cycles, ecofields	Habitat: nesting place, sheltering, moving routes, observation spots, etc.	Partners: relations to species mates and symbionts.	Resources: availability of prey, food, water and other resources.	Enemies and threats: predators, anthropogenic dangers, possibilities for coping with these.	Commentary
Eurasian sparrowhawk (<i>Accipiter nisus</i>)	The wooded meadow is a typical habitat, with good opportunities for shelter. Sparrowhawk uses spruce trees, which are scarce in the area, as nesting sites, and prefers open flight corridors for predation.	Solitary bird, may use the abandoned nests of crows for nesting.	Good food base: the area is home to an abundance of small songbirds and small mammals.	None, tolerates moderate human exposure. Threatened by clear-cutting and land reclamation/construction.	The sparrow hawk has a good foraging habitat in the flooded meadow, but less favorable breeding sites. The species could benefit from the creation of more open areas, while housing development would be detrimental.
Eurasian bullfinch (<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i>)	The overgrown flooded meadow is a suitable habitat, bullfinches' nest in low spruce, but also in bushes. The environment provides shelter and food during the non-breeding period.	Rather solitary, moving in groups during the non-breeding season.	Good food base in the form of diverse vegetation: feeds mainly on seeds, but also on buds and shoots.	Birds of prey, fearful of humans during breeding season. Dense undergrowth for shelter.	The flooded meadow is a suitable nesting and feeding habitat for the Eurasian Bullfinch during the non-breeding period. Opening up the flooded meadow to

					human disturbance would be detrimental to breeding. May move into the city in winter.
Lesser spotted woodpecker (<i>Dryobates minor</i>)	Woodland along riverbanks, with dried and decayed trees, is a good habitat. Woodpecker also forages on reed. Breeds in cavities cut into deciduous trees, and thus requires larger trees.	Rather solitary species but moves in mixed flocks with other small birds.	Diverse natural woodland as a food base. Forages for insects and food in the bark of tree branches.	There are almost no natural enemies. Threatened by clear-cutting and land reclamation/construction.	Species of conservation category III, needs overgrown and wild stands for nesting. May move to urban areas in winter.
Eurasian penduline tit (<i>Remiz pendulinus</i>)	Needs dense riverside thickets and willows to live and nest. Penduline tit builds a characteristic nest on taller deciduous trees growing in swamps but has also nested in reed.	Small in number, rather solitary in life-style.	Insectivorous: beetles, butterflies, spiders. The insect fauna of the flooded meadow is abundant according to wildlife survey databases.	Birds of prey are natural enemies. Needs dense thickets for shelter. Fearful of human interference and disturbance. Threatened by clear-cutting and land reclamation/ construction.	A breeding bird that is typical for the banks of the Emajõgi River, rare elsewhere in Estonia, it needs an undisturbed willow thicket along the river for nesting. Species of symbolic value.
Eurasian beaver (<i>Castor fiber</i>)	Inhabitant of riverine ponds and ditches, it needs access to the river, natural deciduous vegetation, abundant aquatic vegetation for feeding. Old river ponds and ditches of the Kvissentali makes the important habitat. Creates wetlands and shapes wooded meadow habitats for itself and other species.	Creates habitats for aquatic species by felling and drying trees. Flooded areas are used by fish, amphibians and aquatic invertebrates. Creates good growing conditions for aquatic plants. Territory approx. 2 km of riparian zone.	Aquatic vegetation (cattails, reeds, water lilies, etc.), willows and broad-leaved trees in winter.	Young animals can be endangered by ferrets, foxes, and stray dogs. Tolerant of moderate human disturbance. The beaver has been driven out of urban glades due to conflict between human and beaver environmental aesthetics and use. Threatened by	The Kvissental flooded meadow has all the characteristics of a favourable environment for beavers. The beaver is a restorer and shaper of the flooded meadows ecosystem, needs access to water and can tolerate low/moderate human disturbance. It disperses into the city

	There are several traces of beaver activity in the flooded meadows.			restoration of riverbanks.	during the movement of young animals.
European polecat (<i>Mustela putorius</i>)	Riversides and riverside woods are typical habitats, digging burrows on the banks, also using abandoned burrows of beavers.	Solitary species, territorial (territory up to 4 km ²).	Polecat has a varied diet: rodents (mice), amphibians, fish, reptiles, insects, birds and their eggs.	Natural enemies include foxes and dogs, as well as larger birds of prey. Threatened by clear-cutting and land reclamation/construction.	A generalist and omnivore that prefers the banks of watercourses, it tolerates moderate human disturbance.
Roe deer (<i>Capreolus capreolus</i>)	Roe deer prefers mosaic landscapes: typical habitats are ponds, scrub and peri-urban cultivated landscapes, and grasslands for feeding. In winter, the availability of snow-free ground (paths, scrub) and spruce and pine needles is important.	In winter in groups, in summer in families or singly (territory about 1-4 km ²).	A diversity of grasses in the flooded meadows, with willow and other deciduous shoots in winter.	Larger predators, dangerous to lambs are foxes and stray dogs. Roe deer is a game animal.	Prefers a mosaic landscape with openings, tolerates moderate human disturbance. Moves freely and extensively in suburban cultural landscapes.
Common frog (<i>Rana temporaria</i>)	Moist forests, ponds, shady woodland, needs old river bonds for spawning and hibernating (hibernates at the bottom of water bodies). Makes seasonal migrations from Kvissentali flooded meadow to Aruküla plateau. Spawning and hibernation sites are the main ecofields in the flooded meadow.	Local, spawning and wintering in groups, seasonal mass migrations can be up to 10 km long.	Various insects: beetles, amphibods, mollusks, etc. The flooded meadow provides a diverse insect fauna for the common frog to feed on.	Natural enemies are fishes (to tadpoles), snakes, herons, foxes, mustelids (polecat, mink, otter), etc. Predominantly nocturnal species, needs heterogeneous terrain for daytime shelter. It is threatened by the creation of artificial roads and the destruction of spawning/hibernation sites.	The Kvissentali flooded meadow provides spawning and hibernation sites for common frog, as well as a rich food base and good shelter. Presence of inland waterbodies in the flooded meadow is important for the grass frog. The species makes seasonal migrations crossing anthropogenic landscapes.

<p>Northern bat (<i>Eptesicus nilssonii</i>)</p>	<p>An anthropophilic species, it hibernates in cellars, out-buildings, caves, sometimes in tree hollows. Breeding colonies are also often found in buildings. Prefers edges of biotopes, mosaic woodland with glades. The flooded meadow is probably important as a feeding area and resting sites tend to be in surrounding communities.</p>	<p>Colonial species when hibernating and in roosting colonies, they may share shelter with other bat species (e.g. whiskered bat, Brown long-eared bat, Common pipistrelle, etc.).</p>	<p>Main part of the diet is made up of flies (mosquitoes), moths and beetles. The flooded meadow and the proximity of the river provide a rich insect fauna.</p>	<p>There are no natural enemies. Human threats are urbanization and (re)construction of buildings that close off wintering and resting sites, as well as light pollution.</p>	<p>The Kvissentali flooded meadow is an important foraging area for bats due to its proximity to the river and its rich insect fauna. Resting areas are mostly in other nearby biotopes.</p>
<p>Amateur fisherman and walkers (<i>Homo sapiens sapiens</i>)</p>	<p>Riverside open banks, pathways between fishing sites, sitting and camping areas.</p>	<p>Companying pets. For foxes, seagulls and crows, food waste left on the riverbanks.</p>	<p>Different species of fish, invertebrates harvested from river banks, local disturbance of other species by presence. Disturbance of several species by dogs. Food (and waste) brought into the pond from the city.</p>	<p>Potential conflict between different types of environmental use (ecofields): recreational (holidaymakers and hobby fishermen) and habitat/mobility (property development). It does not seem possible to reconcile these functions.</p>	<p>Recreational fishers and walkers have some impact on other species. At the same time, the pond has an important nature education function and a role as a recreational site. Access roads should be constructed in a way that does not reduce the diversity and integrity of the flooded meadow environment.</p>

Summary of the analysis: The Kvissentali flooded meadow is an established rich and diverse natural community that provides essential ecofields and affordances for many species. Although only ten species were included in the analysis, ecological and semiotic relationships between the different species were revealed (facilitation: e.g. beaver burrows as a habitat for polecats; feeding relationships: common frog -> polecats).

From the perspective of the different species, the value of the Kvissentali flooded meadow lies in the species-rich vegetation and insect fauna, which provides a good foraging base (from the model species: common frog, Northern bat), the naturally established deciduous forest, which provides shelter and nesting opportunities (foraging ecofield, shelter ecofield). Willows at the riverbank are important for several species described (from the model species: beaver, Eurasian penduline tit). Here, there may be conflict between human and other species' ecofields: hobby fishermen and recreationalists prefer open riparian areas, which are unfavourable for most of the species observed. Large-scale opening up of riverbanks would have a significant detrimental effect on the ecological habitat of other species.

The movement needs of several species observed between the Kvissentali flooded meadows and other communities should be taken into account (including to the urban areas: from the model species: bullfrog, bullfinch, roe deer). It is important to maintain and create natural links between the flooded meadow and other natural areas, as well as to urban parks (e.g. cemeteries) (mobility ecofield). Creating the open areas with less natural vegetation in the flooded meadow could be beneficial for some of the species observed (from the model species: roe deer, bats). The creation of access roads should maintain the diversity, integrity and heterogeneity of the flooded meadow. Creating the access routes should take into account the interests of other species (green corridors, tunnels for amphibians, footpaths for humans).

The creation of pathways would allow better access and contact for people with the rich biota of the flooded meadow (as recreation area). On the other hand, increased human impact (housing development, light traffic routes and roads) would be significantly detrimental to the interests of a number of the species considered. In the context of the Kvissentali flooded meadow, the different human ecofields are conflicting and incompatible: the habitat ecofield (residential development) and the recreational ecofield (the flooded meadow as an unspoilt natural community near the city).

APPENDIX 4. SHORT LL REPORTS ON UMWELTS, AFFORDANCES, AND NONHUMANS

Healing gardens, Budapest, Hungary LL

Name of person(s) who filled in the form: György Pataki and Beáta Pántya

1. What has been the experience with umwelt thinking / analysis in your Living Lab so far?

So far, we have been using 4 techniques related to umwelt thinking: *Walking autoethnography and nonparticipant observation*: Regularly, a researcher slowly walks around the garden, visiting every part and records her/his experience, including (i) her/his encounters with other species (recording the species, what that creature seems to be doing) and (ii) her/his observations of how other humans use the garden (what other humans are doing in the garden). *Sit Spot autoethnography*: A specific location in the garden is selected where time is regularly spent there sitting, observing and connecting with the natural surroundings in a mindful and intentional way. By sitting and listening, experiences are constantly recorded in the form of written notes. *Soundscapes*: By recording sounds throughout the day and night, we can listen to the garden's voices and identify species that may not be visible to us. Also, we can observe the dynamics of the garden's voices across the seasons. *Timelapses*: Extended-duration timelapses that capture the seasonal transformations also facilitate the observation of territorial changes and the interactions among the living organisms in those areas.

2. What is the main role or function of non-human species in your Living Lab? If possible, please specify the species.

In general, the hospital garden currently resembles an urban park, not too rich in plant and animal species. There are 5 parts of the hospital garden with clearly defined boundaries: large meadow, inner garden, rear meadow, shady park, vegetable garden. Some members of the medical staff and some of the patients clearly enjoy human-nonhuman encounters, particularly animal-human encounters. Species highly valued in this regard includes primarily bird species, e.g. swallows, great tits, blue tits, goldcrests, etc. (typically spotted in the bushes of the large meadow, on trees of the shady park, and the nests on the buildings). Some animals, particularly cats, evoke opposing feelings. Among the plant species, trees tend to be valued much due to their providing shade during the heat (shady park). Some tree species, e.g. willow, enjoy symbolic values to some garden users (large meadow). Some therapists also incorporate observing the condition of plants and the changes in their life cycles into therapy. Of course, open space (large meadow, rear meadow) in the garden is also valuable for physical exercises or collective sport activities. There is a smaller vegetable plot cultivated by some of the patients during horticulture therapy sessions. Some patients are attached to particular plants, e.g. flowers and herbs (inner garden), which they also care for in their daily routines.

3. What are the key affordances (i.e. characteristics of the environment that enable activities) in your Living Lab for human and non-human species?

The approx. 3 ha large hospital garden provides multiple affordances. The hospital garden is large and diverse enough to provide space for walking, jogging, yoga, tai chi, and collective sport activities (for the latter, esp. the flat parts of the large and rear meadows). The shady park invites more contemplative, meditative use. The inner garden is typically used for group therapy sessions and individual caring for flower and herb beds. There are some hidden, bushy areas where intimate activities happen. Bird feeders attract many birds during the feeding season. The feeding is carried out by the hospital staff and patients. There are also several birdhouses in the garden, inhabited by bird species characteristic of the area, such as blue tits.

Molentargius-Saline Regional Nature Park, Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy LL

Name of person(s) who filled in the form: Oriana Mosca, Silvana Mula, Ferdinando Fornara

1. What has been the experience with umwelt thinking/analysis in your Living Lab so far?

We tried to consider as many expert points of view as possible, which could know, to some extent even the voice of non-humans (e.g., ornithologists, biologists, salt marsh experts). We conducted the interviews with experts by walking along different Park trails, to have an experience of different micro-environments. Umwelt analysis allowed the team to delve more into interconnection of different species that is based on delicate balances that can be challenged by both events beyond human control (e.g., heatwaves and subsequent wildfires) and by threats posed by humans (e.g., vandalism). The umwelt analysis inspired the Cagliari team for the creation of the Ecopoly game played during the Cagliari workshop meeting. Indeed, the story was built around a conflict arising from two different forces, the salt producers in the salt pan oriented by profit motivation and the park guardians, motivated by environmental conservation and protection motives. The three interviews conducted has led the Cagliari team to plan the realization of new interviews through umwelt analysis with other experts, such as herpetologists, to capture more unheard voices (and in this case unseen images since reptilians and amphibians have an hiding nature) and in other seasons. Flora until now was not investigated and mentioned, but we are interested in providing an analysis of its precious role in the Park life through the realization of some interviews with experienced botanists.

2. What is the main role or function of non-human species in your Living Lab? If possible, please specify the species.

Because of its natural geographic location and the various ecological niches within it, which are optimal for roosting and wintering, the Molentargius ecosystem allows the massive presence of resident, breeding and passage birds, about one-third of the European avifauna; including many EU-protected species.

In Molentargius Park, non-human species play key *ecological* as well as educational roles. Pink flamingos are a key species, also called “umbrella species,” whose presence is indicative of the health of the park's wetlands. These birds not only contribute to biodiversity but also attract visitors, raising awareness and interest in environmental conservation. Other important species include various waterfowl species, such as herons, sultan chickadees, and egrets, which help maintain the ecological balance through their feeding and nesting habits.

The Molentargius ecosystem is also important for animal species belonging to other classes, however less known and more difficult to identify than birds. Examples of such classes are, among the Amphibians: the Tree Frog, and the Emerald Toad; among the Reptiles: the Marsh Turtle, the Water Snake, the Leopard, and the Luscengola; and among the Mammals: the Hedgehog, the Weasel, and the Wild Rabbit.

Balance among non-human species like avifauna and the presence of other species, like for example *Artemia Salina*, and the presence of vegetation is essential. The *Artemia Salina* is a small crustacean living in environments where there is high salinity and is *Phoenicopterus roseus* favourite food. The tiny arthropod is rich in beta-carotene, a red-orange pigment that settles in the feathers of the flamingos giving them the characteristic pink colour. In Sardinia, pink flamingos are called “Sa Genti Arrubia” meaning “red people”.

Harmonization and balance among species are both vital.

From the results of different investigations carried out from the 1970s until present time, it can be concluded that Molentargius has been seriously compromised as a result of improper land use, which has damaged the ecosystem, in general, and the flora in particular. Therefore, a careful evaluation of actual data (i.e., updated mapping of all taxa of fauna and flora) is necessary in order to safeguard what is still present and possibly try to restore more natural conditions, preventing non-native plants from gaining the upper hand, resulting as a threat for other species. Despite this, the territory of the Park still represents a great natural heritage, both for flora and fauna, which needs to be safeguarded and enhanced. Knowledge of the different naturalistic components is absolutely necessary to be able to operate in the best possible way in any territory and, in particular, in such unique and fragile habitats as are the wetland environments. The information provided by studies on the naturalistic component will be able to enable the Park Authority to develop strategies for targeted management that will, perhaps, make possible the coexistence of environmental peculiarities with the needs of humans.

Beyond educational function, some species, like bees, are employed also for food purposes. There are some projects, like the “BeePark” project, devoted to the joint development of people’s environmental awareness and delicious honey to taste. There are also projects using olive trees and officinal plants, all under the supervision of experts.

3. What are the key affordances (i.e. characteristics of the environment that enable activities) in your Living Lab for human and non-human species?

Molentargius Park is a multifaceted park, encompassing a natural protected park, a city park for recreational activities, and a historical-cultural park.

For non-humans: The Molentargius-Saline Living Lab is a wetland, providing essential nesting, feeding and resting habitats for migratory birds. The park is rich in natural vegetation, which provides shelter and food resources for various animal species, and expanses of bodies of water, essential for the survival of fish and waterfowl.

For humans: The Park offers a vast area in which to enjoy recreational activities such as jogging, meditation, and picnicking, as well as educational activities such as birdwatching, sheep and beekeeping classes, and nature workshops. As the summer period approaches, human activities within the park are less frequent, due to the great heat during daylight hours, and due to the invasion of mosquitoes during afternoon/evening hours. Because of the few areas of shade for humans, pine trees, which are an allochthonous species of Molentargius Park, were artificially planted a few years ago in order to allow humans to carry out their activities.

Cross-border virtual commons / Beskydy, Czechia, Slovakia LL

Name of person(s) who filled in the form: Jiří Louda

1. What has been the experience with umwelt thinking / analysis in your Living Lab so far?

Before the project started, we did not work directly with the umwelt concept, nobody was familiar with this concept, although implicitly it was de facto used by some stakeholders. For example, the State Nature Conservancy deals with how to create the most suitable conditions for the occurrence of rare butterfly species, as well as are creating (or trying to create) friendly environment for amphibians, protected plants and other species. Some experts have a very good understanding of what selected animal and plant species need to flourish.

In the previous Interreg project we also mapped suitable habitats in the region to support biodiversity which are suitable for further protection: <https://gis.nlcsk.org/beskydy/#>. There were also other projects which e.g. dealt with mapping of lynx and their migration corridors which resulted in changes in the environment to make it more suitable for these predators (e.g. demolition of fences, etc.) – see more: <https://www.selmy.cz/clanky/jak-se-dari-vysadbe-v-migracnim-koridoru-u-jablunkova-a-co-prinesla-telemetrie-beskydskych-rysu/>

We are currently opening the discussion with local stakeholders about possibilities of adapting the current governance approaches to transform the environment in a way to make it more sustainable for both, human and non-humans (the special needs of non-humans will also be considered). E.g. more frequent use of natural forest regeneration and integrate these affordances to Coevolvers Ecopoly-RBG. Another example of methods of gentle mowing of grass in meadows, which would support biodiversity more and think about, for example, all developmental stages of insects (caterpillar, pupa, adult individual – butterfly)

2. What is the main role or function of non-human species in your Living Lab? If possible, please specify the species.

Main important non-human species for our LL are currently spruces as the main type of trees in the local forests. In future it will be other types of trees (oaks, beeches, firs, maple trees, larches) since the local monocultural spruce forests will change in forest with high diversity of tree species and age structure in reaction to climate change. Until recently the main role of trees in the region was timber production, however the view of their role has been changing recently by local people. They realize that healthy close to nature forest are also important for retaining water, supporting biodiversity, microclimate regulation and the overall functioning of the local ecosystem.

Very important species are deer, roe deer and other type of game. These animals are an integral part of the local environment, however if overpopulated, they can have a negative impact on efforts to change forest structure (tasting of young sprouts).

Other important non-human species is sheep as locally traditional farm animal that not only brings sustenance (meat, milk, cheese) to humans, but are also crucial for other (engendered) species. Sheep have grazed the grasslands for centuries, allowing rare plant species and associated insects to grow.

Invasive species that threaten fauna and flora are appearing in some places (Jewelweed, Cow Parsnip, Common raccoon dog, Raccoon)

Wolves and bears are also important species specific to this site. Especially on the Czech side of the Living lab, it is the only site in Czechia where the bears are regularly living. On the other hand, locals have an ambivalent relationship with these species – damage to livestock (sheeps).

Other important species are butterflies, grouse, eagles. They are taken as indicators of environmental quality.

3. What are the key affordances (i.e. characteristics of the environment that enable activities) in your Living Lab for human and non-human species?

There are two key affordances: i) High-quality biodiverse forests, which are resilient to upcoming nature changes. Such a forest should provide suitable conditions for all key species while supporting the well-being of the local human population; ii) the ability of the environment to retain water. For this purpose it is necessary to change the species and age structure of the forest and to create conditions for water retention in the landscape (NBS implementation), which requires broad cooperation between local stakeholders. New NBS very often also support biodiversity and provides habitats for multiple species (e.g. ponds for retaining water in forests, multi-species forest, traditionally maintained meadows, agroforestry, etc.)

Murray Park, Alford, Scotland LL

Name of person(s) who filled in the form: Claire Hardy; Tim Pittaway; Acacia Marshall; Leanne Townsend

Summary:

1. The methods used to inform this work were primarily the interviews and therefore Annex 5. This was supplemented with walking discussions, emails, informal chats and workshops.

2. The role and function of non-humans in the LL

- Many non-humans are considered welcome visitors or residents, whilst other non-humans although nice to observe are often identified as having negatives attributed to their presence. Examples of non-humans are:
- Red squirrels are identified as iconic and people are happy to see them, food, is placed in gardens to encourage them to visit and stay in the surrounding area.
- Deer although nice to spot are associated with destruction of the habitat and have environmental consequences on NBS. Destruction of newly planted trees and set back to trees becoming established were a negative voiced by LL members.
- There is a diverse bird population, whilst some LL members can identify them by sight and sound others just appreciate their presence, sometimes just as a comforting noise.
- The trees are identified as playing a crucial role both as part of the woodland ecosystem but also as species that are an integral part of the natural wild space and go further to enhance the enjoyment of both the human visitors and non-human residents.

3. Key affordances identified were:

- The park is valued by the community and recognised as a 'magical place'. The LL members mention a feeling of wellbeing and belonging.
- They identify the space offers affordances for the dogs being walked there, providing an area rich in smells impacting positivity on the dog's quality of life. The dogs perceive the affordances the woodland habitat offers, by displaying positive behaviour.
- Fallen trees offer entertainment for humans and living spaces for many non-humans.
- Whilst living trees offer habitats for living and sources of food for diverse number of non-humans.
- Conflict of affordances are seen between non-humans.
 - Pine martens and red squirrels
 - Red and grey squirrels
 - Mink and duck and voles
- and humans and non-humans
 - Deer
 - Badgers
- Impact on the affordances by humans was commented on, presence of commercial foragers.
- Climate change impact on affordances were described.

Detailed Affordances analysis

1. What has been the experience with umwelt thinking / analysis in your Living Lab so far?

Our reflections on umwelt in Murray Park are derived from our interactions with the LL members in interviews, walking conversations, and workshops including Searching for Common Ground. Further insights have been gathered from LL core members (especially the Murray Park Trustees) through email conversations. During the interviews the concept of umwelt and affordances was not introduced directly. Instead, reflections were gathered from LL stakeholders on the LL non-humans and the space they occupied. Umwelt thinking was introduced during the activity exploring Searching for Common Ground which engaged with LL stakeholders in mapping and identifying areas of the woodland important to the community. This activity was participatory and visual, using hands-on and sharing methods to elicit discussion and gather information. As part of this exercise, LL stakeholders mapped the areas important for various non-human species and how both humans and non-humans use these habitats.

Conducting informal walking conversations with some of the users in Murray Park enhanced the researcher's understanding of the woodland ecosystem. This allowed researchers to observe and interact with the environment directly, noting the interrelationships between community and nature and their habitats. This engagement encourages LL members to draw attention to specific non-human (as well as human/non-human) interactions and processes as they occur along the woodland paths. Additionally, for the researcher and LL members, being in the woodland stimulates the senses, which can prompt detailed, context-rich discussions that might not emerge in a traditional interview setting.

Our understandings have been further informed by ongoing communications with the LL stakeholders, whether by email, or by informal meet ups in the woodland itself (bearing in mind that one of the Hutton team lives close to the woodland and walks there nearly daily, as well as playing a role on the Trust of the woodland itself).

2. What is the main role or function of non-human species in your Living Lab? If possible, please specify the species.

The non-human species in this mixed woodland habitat are typical for the area and include several of interest, such as red squirrels, badgers, and otters:

'Red squirrels are! I mean, honestly, people are passionate about red squirrels. So, if you've got an iconic species that people can relate to.'

These species are popular with the public, and Murray Park offers a unique opportunity to observe wildlife up close, conveniently located near Alford village. Roe deer are frequently observed in the area, and whilst some LL members point out that they enjoy seeing them, others highlight that their browsing of tree saplings hinders forest regeneration (tree tubes are necessary to protect the newly planted tree saplings):

'Deer having a negative influence. It falls to humans to manage the deer population, but that also needs to be communicated well to the community because you know, so that they're not seen as being something bad and that'

'Deer are a horrendous issue. We've just been commenting on... [REDACTED FORESTRY COMPANY NAME] are gonna be restocking a wood near us and we want them to plant broadleaves, but they just won't survive. So forestry is incredibly compromised by deer here.'

Other species mentioned by LL stakeholders include: hedgehogs, pine martens and various species of smaller mammals (that are often prey for various birds). There is a diverse bird population including great spotted woodpeckers, tree creepers and sparrowhawks, spotted flycatchers, grey wagtail, and woodcocks. Birds are really abundant in the woodland, with many LL members referring to their importance:

'I mean when I go there in June, I just can't believe how many willow warblers there are. And for most people, it's just birds twittering. They probably like the birds twittering but they don't know what they are.'

Some of the wildlife in Murray Park, i.e. amphibians and insects, are more active during the breeding seasons.

Various species of plants are considered vital – especially trees which play a critical role in a woodland ecosystem:

'Well, obviously the trees themselves because of the tree planting.... I mean, you've got quite a strong deer, a roe deer population. You've got squirrels, which if you come out and look at that back of our house, all over the red squirrels. I would say that if nothing had been done to the park, they would be the same. So I don't think that there have been things that improve the quality of life for a squirrel or a deer, birds or whatever. Because that takes me back to what I said at the beginning. It's a wildlife area, and therefore you could say the wilder the better. " 'Been the additional planting of a range of broadly native tree species in an area that's relatively dominated by silver birch. So trying to diversify the forest structure. So that was completed by the community, lots of contributions. And yeah, trees seem to have established well, the protection for the trees has been upgraded to cope with herbivore impact.'

One area of great importance to the human LL members is fungi, as several of the local community pick fungi for food:

'I mean I love going to [REDACTED GREENSPACE NAME] because I think "This is, you know, a [place] that I'm involved with and I get my chanterelles... And there's plenty for everybody – well, not all, not the commercial pickers.' [the woodland] is very good for fungi. I mean, nationally important – this woman I met said it's nationally important for fungi, which is quite unusual! Considering it's not that old, it's not like an ancient woodland, you know, so in terms of mycorrhiza and things. It's odd why it's so important when it's not that old'

Further, rare species of mushrooms such as Chaga (*Inonotus obliquus*) have been observed in the woodland, with concerns over commercial pickers targeting and depleting these important resources. This was highlighted in discussion at the Searching for Common Ground workshop.

3. What are the key affordances (i.e. characteristics of the environment that enable activities) in your Living Lab for human and non-human species?

The woodland trees and undergrowth, the varied terrain, from tree clearings and wetlands to dense forests, afford spaces for different ecosystems, while the presence of burns and ponds provides water sources and supports a woodland ecosystem.

Water-related species are important in the woodland too. The pond is an important habitat for the frogs and frog spawn. This brings a lot to children engaging in pond dipping. Small frogs eat insects such as flies and moths, as well as snails, slugs and worms. They use long tongues and sticky saliva to catch prey that passes them by. Tadpoles eat algae in the ponds they grow in. As they grow, they feed on plants and small insects. If there isn't enough food available they might even eat their fellow tadpoles.

'I suppose cause I've done a lot with the pond at the park, and you know when you get to the amphibians breeding and it can be something that people do notice, especially when they're moving to and from the ponds.....Yeah, the bird life. And the fish as well. That is something that's valued by part of the community. Yeah.'

The woodland provides an important place for community members to exercise and spend time. This became especially evident during Covid-19 restrictions:

'Also the quality of the nature. I think it's quite important for [REDACTED PLACE NAME] because it's quite unusual, the site. To be able to go for a walk in a natural wood, you know... It was interesting in COVID when everyone couldn't go very far, and everyone was walking along the roads... And in some ways it was quite nice because there were no cars but I... just everyone was walking on roads everywhere ... What was I saying? Oh yes, quality. Yes, quality of the environment. I don't just wanna go for a walk anywhere, I want to go for a walk in a nice place.'

Community members are very fond of the space and spend a lot of time there – it is especially popular with people walking dogs. It is not only beneficial for dogs, in terms of exercise, but also their psychological wellbeing – for example, LL stakeholders told us in the Searching for Common Ground workshop that dogs enjoy the opportunity to take in the smells in the woodland, it impacts positively on the quality of life of their dogs.

'We become very close to the park. We use it all the time, mainly. Well, for dog walking '.

The woodland is also used by special interest groups, for example Outdoor Woodland Learning groups (OWLS) which use it for outdoor education of children:

Comment about OWLS (workshop): 'Yeah, also because they use that space to help children understand and explore nature'.

Certain aspects of the woodland afford different qualities for different stakeholders. For example, fallen trees provide food and shelter for fungi and insects, but recreational exploratory opportunities for human children, as pointed out by one of the Trustees of the woodland when describing the importance of biodiversity in human-nature connection:

'So fallen trees provide so many opportunities for kids. If there wasn't anything there apart from a monoculture of crop, trees, the opportunities for nature connection are diminished and therefore, are we meeting our aims? We're not meeting all of our aims I guess, if there isn't the diversity there.'

Another way to consider the affordances of the woodland is in terms of what different species bring to one another. E.g. strong soil which includes a healthy mycorrhizal network can support plant life, including trees:

'Yeah I know, it's really odd. And I keep going on about how I can't believe how well these trees have done that we've planted, and somebody said it's the soil and if it's got good mycorrhiza then the trees... And I thought, what is it about [REDACTED GREENSPACE NAME] that the trees grow so well? And someone said, well, it might be the lack of disturbance to the soil because it's not been ploughed for years, so you've got really good soil fauna and mycorrhiza and stuff... So it's just ideal situation to put trees in and they grow. So it's a magical magical place.'

Whilst wildlife derives essential habitat and food from the tree species in the woodland, humans derive a different kind of benefit thanks to the beauty the non-humans bring to the local environment:

'Well, if they're planting trees, obviously they're going to take a few years to grow, but so much benefits from that. If you plant a tree because you're going to have places for nesting, you're going to have food and seeds and whatever comes off the trees. For the birds and all the animals, and if they're just planting bulbs, humans get benefits from that because they're beautiful.....'

Some species are in conflict with one another, particularly non-native species such as mink, and grey squirrels which threaten native red squirrel populations (but thankfully are not currently present in the woodland):

'There was talk of there being a pine martin in the park, which isn't good for red squirrels, but that's nature'

'The other one was grey squirrels, but I don't think that's been an issue here for a long time. And there were mink down by the river, but I think they were controlled.'

'The other thing is that the North American mink, which predate on a lot of the native species are damaging to duck, wildflowers, bank voles, water voles. Other protected species, and they were numerous in that corridor, and they've been reduced effectively'

Non-native plant species are also an issue:

'The giant hogweed's been because the giant hogweed seeds can lie dormant for up to 20 years. It'd be foolish to say it's eradicated.'

'I can take you to an area [of Japanese knotweed] of about the size of a football pitch. That's two acres. Yeah. Huge, huge areas that I've never been sprayed or contaminated. And the Himalayan balsam, which is also edible. Yah, but once again, there's been efforts to reduce this population.'

There are occasions where non-native species are considered acceptable however, due to the affordances they bring for important species:

'If we want to put a Norway spruce in there we will, because the squirrels like them – they're not native, but I'll bung them in.'

Conflict also exists between non humans and humans, e.g.:

Badgers: 'Some people think they're cute... But I'm not of that opinion! [laughs] ... Well they're very destructive in terms of the land.....you can tell the holes and the whole thing's really been destroyed by the burrowing and the digging. We had somebees that were in the ground, and they burrowed into that to eat the honey ... Being of an agricultural persuasion, I still think they're responsible for TB, so... Yeah, so I don't really have anything good to say about badgers!'

'I think people, generally speaking, are very excited when they see, depending who you speak to deer, foxes, badgers, pine martens, mink, which we'll call AA predators, which are capable of damage to businesses, infrastructure banks, so on and so forth.'

This can even be said for the use of the woodland between different human stakeholders. For example, the use of the woodland by commercial foragers might deplete the availability of edible fungi for local community members.

Humans also often make efforts to enhance the affordances for nonhuman species in the woodland. For example, many bird boxes were installed in Murray Park, which serve as essential affordances for birds, providing them with safe and suitable environments to nest and rear their young. These structures offer protection from harsh weather conditions and create a secure habitat. It is also common for people to provide food to wildlife:

'But I do have this kind of love to see a red squirrel in the garden, or hear a black cap sing, or a goldfinch or siskins? And the answer is absolutely I do. And I feed them as well and encourage them in terms of that engagement.'

Woodlands create a secure microclimate by regulating temperature and retaining moisture. The canopy cover provided by trees offers shade, reducing ground temperatures and mitigating the effects of temperature extremes. Murray Park forms a lowland wetland and exhibits a "sponge effect," which plays a crucial role in hydrological cycles and the catchment of flooding from Alford village. This sponge effect refers to forested areas' ability to absorb and retain significant amounts of water during high rainfall. A subtle ridge in the park partially demarcates two main burns (streams) in Murray Park; these waterways converge with the River Don and form part of a greater water catchment area. The waterlogged part of the woodland is home to species of amphibians and otters, and high humidity supports the growth of mosses and ferns. The decomposition of dead wood and damp conditions offers significant ecological benefits. Water-saturated, decaying wood can attract and support water-borne species. (Expert description of the park).

Some LL members have highlighted the impacts that climate change is already having on the non-humans and the affordances found in the woodland:

'It would be foolish not to wonder if it's connected to climate change, and so if that's happening to bees which are being costed and looked after, the assumption would be the pollinators, the bombus terrestris species, are struggling equally.'

'this year was quite a wet, sort of humid summer. So some of the mushrooms thrived better. It was such a good year for chanterelles, but then it wasn't such a good year for the ceps because the flies love them.'

'we've had like long dry periods and that seems to have increased fire risks, things like that. You know, less rainfall than we should have been having. And then on the other hand getting in the last few weeks, would we say half a year's rain falling? Well, yeah. Going back to the butterflies and how Scotland appeared to be kind of bucking the trend and showing an increase. That's just really with some of the more habitat generalist species moving further north, so showing that increase, but that was masking some of the other habitat specialist declining. You know, less connectivity in the landscape for things to move about, yeah.'

Finally LL members noted funding is required to help provide access to nature for people, physical barriers in the natural environment prevent humans accessing the woodland. In Murray Park, funding has helped the Trust members to develop new "all accessibility" paths, which are increasing inclusivity by enabling wheelchairs users to have access to the woodland and experience nature.

Turku, Finland LL

Name of person(s) who filled in the form: Kia Andell

1. What has been the experience with umwelt thinking / analysis in your Living Lab so far?

We have been interested in employing umwelt analysis to improve our understanding of the Pansio-Perno neighborhood as a non-human environment, as well as interactions, encounters and possible conflicts between humans and non-humans in the area. For this purpose, we have developed a citizen science app that also has a storytelling component, arranged a nature walk with an ecologist and carried out some observations in the area that, although mainly focused on human affordances of different places, also pay some attention to non-humans observed. So far, we still have quite little practical experience of applying umwelt methods in the Pansio-Perno neighborhood but after the summer holidays we seek to emphasize umwelt thinking in our activities.

2. What is the main role or function of non-human species in your Living Lab? If possible, please specify the species.

Pansio-Perno is a very green neighborhood with many kinds of nature types and habitats and a range of different species can be found in the area. Flying squirrel is one very important species since its habitats have to be taken into consideration in all kinds of development plans in the green areas, including socio-ecological compensation measures. There are also some other protected animals, like frogs and bats whose habitats may affect land-use in the area. Birds are particularly important for local residents and a variety of different bird species can be found in the area. Both organizations and private citizens have been active in e.g. building bird houses, and many residents who have gardens also seek to make them attractive places to butterflies and other pollinators. Most conflicts, on the other hand, are related to deers that regularly visit people's gardens. However, the residents also have come up with

creative ways to minimize harm the deers may cause in gardens and live in harmony with them.

3. What are the key affordances (i.e. characteristics of the environment that enable activities) in your Living Lab for human and non-human species?

- The Raisio river bank: important recreational area for humans, e.g. jogging, fishing, and habitat for many kinds of birds and other species; also some field on the other side → growing plants, food for birds
- Lots of green areas connected to each other, various habitats and possibilities to move for animals
- Some large areas with little human impact: on one hand, restricted access to humans that decreases affordances for them, on the other hand, peaceful places for animals and also e.g. lots of dead trees that serve as habitats for many insects
- Human-made places like gardens that serve food for e.g. birds and pollinators (as well as deers..); Bird houses in the yards of city-owned buildings and in companies' areas; Companies have carried out some conservation measures, e.g. the Meyer shipyard has created a place that represents endangered habitat.

APPENDIX 5. NON-HUMAN LETTERS AND AFFORDANCE MOSAICS

Non-human letters – visualized short narratives. Sample letter of the Eurasian beaver (*Castor fiber*):

I am Beaver. My home is upstream from a town, and I have lived there for three winters. I have built my lodge in one of the many shallow channels that flow into the river. Riverbanks with natural vegetation provide me with food. I also need large trees – willows, birches, alders – that grow near the water to survive the winters. It is my nature to build dams and flood the land. This may be unpleasant for you. But my dams and ditches also create habitats for fish, frogs, mayflies, diving beetles and others. So, what I do brings life to the riverbanks. I worry about roads coming too close to my home because they change the way the water moves. I also fear unleashed dogs and noisy machinery that I do not understand. Otherwise, I like living on the edge of town because many of my natural enemies – lynx, wolves, bears – do not come here.

Affordance mosaics – vizualisation of affordances. A sample, is based on the information gained from the umwelt-based place analysis of Tartu LL, and represents the landscape as meaningful to three species: humans (recreational fishermen), beavers and penduline tit

